

**Mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of
marketing on car purchasing intention Sri Lanka**

This dissertation is submitted for the degree of (DBA)

Doctor of Business Administration

By

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Abstract

Background: With the growing environmental issues, people are more concern about securing environment and situation has led change in consumer purchasing approach towards a eco-friendly lifestyle. Therefore, companies also are being transforming to eco-friendly aspects of marketing through implementing green marketing strategies to achieve sustainable competitive advantage. The green marketing has verity of advantages for the companies in terms of increasing brand image and achieving sustainable environmental benefits. This research focuses on the eco-friendly aspects of marketing on consumer purchase intention with the consideration of brand image as a mediator.

Aim: The aim of this research study is to analyse and evaluate Mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on car purchasing intention Sri Lanka.

Methods: The sample size selected for this study was 384 respondents who are frequent visitors to car dealer companies and most of them own a car. As the sample population, consumers have been selected to determine the effectiveness of the Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on Car purchasing Intention Sri Lanka. To identify the managerial perspectives of eco-friendly marketing and the consumer purchase behaviour, the interview sample has been decided with the participants from each district of the country. Depending on this, managers of different car brands, existing car owners, government officers, students and other professionals chosen and interviewed for qualitative data collection and analysis.

Findings: Through the quantitative research method of this research, it has been identified the various relationship between purchase intention and the variables such as environmental awareness, green perceived value, green trust, and mediating effect of brand image. SPSS statistical software and PROCESS tool are used to test the hypotheses and to reach the objectives. Qualitative research method has been used to get the managerial and consumer perceptions about the eco-friendly aspects of marketing on purchase intention.

Conclusion: This research has reflected upon the eco-friendly aspects of marketing in car dealer companies in Sri Lanka. The impact of environmental awareness, green trust, perceived quality, and mediating role of the brand image on purchase intention of Sri Lankan consumers also been showed throughout this research. This research has shown the influences of eco-friendliness when consumers purchase their cars which impact on business functions of the car

dealer companies/marketers in auto industry in Sri Lanka. The relationships between green marketing factors and purchase intention have been also successfully derived throughout this research.

Key words: Green Marketing, Purchasing Intention, Brand Image, Green trust, Perceived Quality

SYNONYMS

Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
Chief Executive Officer (CEO)
Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)
zero-emission vehicle (ZEV)
Multinational corporations (MNCs)
South Asia (SA)
Central Bank of Sri Lanka (CBSL)
Gross Domestic Production (GDP)
United Kingdom (UK)
United States (US)
non-government Organisations (NGO)
Road and Motor Vehicle (RMV)
statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS)
Theory of planned Behaviour (TPB)
Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT)
Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)
Internal Combustion Engine (ICE)

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Recently people around the world have been facing for environmental challenges such as global warming, air quality contamination, climate change, energy security and resources scarcity, resulting in huge pressure to reduce the human ecological footprint by adopting to sustainable products and consumption (Nicholas et, al., 2018). Environmental concern has been given most priority among general public in any government across the world and many of them have taken first steps as it is a collective responsibility of everyone who live in the earth (Ulla A. Saari a, b, Saku J. Makinen € a , Rupert J. Baumgartner c , Bas Hillebrand d, e , Paul H. Driessen, 2020).

Burning coal to generate electricity produces toxic gases and has been the single biggest contributor to climate change as discussed in COP26 (Mountford et al., 2021). It also come up with an idea that Protecting and restoring ecosystems, and managing land sustainably, has the potential to reduce annual net greenhouse gas emissions by more than 7 giga tons by 2030 (Mountford et al., 2021). Similarly, the 2009 climate change act for Scotland has set up targets to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 to 80% in comparison with the emission level in 1990 (Milev et al., 2021). As such various authorities have taken viable options to protect the environment by reducing greenhouse gas emission.

Moreover, COP26, 2021 has mentioned that road transport has accounted 10% of world's greenhouse gas emissions and by avoiding the Carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the road transport can be achieved through the decarbonisation of road transportation system by 2030. As a result, they have agreed that to transform to zero emission road transport technology. As per the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of Volvo car production, transformation to zero emission automobile production has not only positively contributed to the planet but also for the company's future growth and sustainability. Therefore, they have been identified the need of accelerate transition to zero emission vehicle to achieve climate change goal and reduce the emission from the air we breathe (Cohen et, al., 2022).

The world population has increased drastically over the past few decades. (Milev et al., 2021) It has been a threat in both developed and developing countries which caused ecological pressure and adversely affected to the environment. Eco-innovation and eco-friendly

consumption have come to play as a critical area of sustainable development. Eco-friendly consumption has led to people purchase green items which necessary to protect the environment while non-eco-friendly buying behaviour has caused to an environmental damage. Therefore, there is a need of adhere for the eco-friendly purchase behaviour. (Wijekoon and Sabri , 2021). Moreover, even consumer think that it is a responsibility of the consumers to purchase green products, that was not only the consumer's responsibility but also producers have a responsibility to produce eco-friendly products to minimise the pollution. Therefore, most of the companies have already been transferred to the environmentally friendly production processes, eco-friendly products as well as implementing green marketing concept to their marketing strategy (Nicholas et, al., 2018).

In supportive with the above, policy makers also have been responsible to spread the usefulness and the benefit of the usage of the electric cars in different ways even in some countries they have not yet been popular. Electric car buyers should incorporate to the mass media to give a publicity to the rest of the potential buyers about the usefulness and the general use. Similarly, interaction among the electric car owners and the interested people should be promoted (Bobeth, Kastner ,2020). Additionally, they have a responsibility towards the providing sufficient financial support, infrastructure, and energy-efficient technologies to promote electric cars.

Researchers have discussed about firms and the environment several time in the academic literature while it was a main topic among the professionals too (Starik & Marcus, 2000). Fast weakening of eco system has become an attracted topic not only the scientists but also in the corporate world to rethink their corporate social responsibilities (CSR) (Nikolaeva and Bicho, 2011). However, the reduction in environmental positive impact has been a big challenge to many companies in different industries including automobile industry. Some car companies also have already adopted to the zero emission cars and vans including 35 countries, 6 major carmakers, 43 cities, states, and regions, 28 fleet owners and 15 financial institutions and investors (Mountford et al., 2021). Most of the countries have transferred to production of electric cars and used them but it has lower level due to the higher purchase price for the consumers. Because householders' moral and social motives such as income and the purpose of the acquisition, status of behaviour have been different from each other. (Bobeth and Kastner , 2020) Automobile manufacturers accounted for more than 30% of the global market have taken steps to discontinue the fossil fuel vehicles recently. General Motors, Jaguar, Fiat, Volvo,

Audi, Ford, and Volkswagen in Europe have all committed to 100% zero-emission vehicle (ZEV) production by 2035. Similarly, other major worldwide car producers such as Aston Martin, Jaguar Land Rover have also published plans to move into the manufacturing of electric or hybrid cars during the next decade. Therefore, there is a higher potential for an electric car market even for new entrants (Le Quéré, Corinne, et al., 2020). As a result, investigation of the car industry in terms of the environment is an essential.

Many multinational corporations (MNCs) have taken serious attention on the environmental protection, and they have reflected that in their CSR disclosures to show their commitments towards the environment and society. In line with that, most MNCs in the automotive industry have moved to transparent disclosures of their social and environmental impact from their activities. As such, companies have put their highest attention to protect the environment as a requirement of CSR policies which shows their credibility. More specifically, the trend of adopting better CSR policies, automotive companies are actively engaging to enhance visibility for reputation and legitimacy purposes (Alessandra et al., 2016).

Still, green marketing or the eco-friendly marketing concepts have not been used in the discussion in a deep manner in many of the literatures. It is a very important consideration to understand the outcomes and it is further discussed in a clear manner to manage the necessary deliveries in the most effective manner in managing discussions on the green marketing actions and green management actions in the organizations which shows the lack of discussion. Thus, the current research has been done in order to fill this research gap. The Sri Lankan automobile industry is in the lack of studies and there is no huge focus in the recent studies on the automobile industry making a knowledge gap in the literature. Accordingly, there is a gap prevailing in the existing literature and there is a gap in the knowledge shares in the literature as well. Along with these identifications, it is counted as very important and needed to consider these identifications and actions to manage the filling of the research gaps in the most effective manner.

1.2 Practical Problem

Global car industry has been declined after the Covid-19 pandemic and it has impacted for the whole world without restricting to a specific region. Like many other industries, car industry also named as one of the biggest one which dropped due to the pandemic (Chowdhury et al, 2020). The Asia-pacific region is accounted for the biggest car production volume (over 62% of the global production) from the global car production while China produces the half of the car production from the Asian production (Le Quéré, Corinne, et al., 2020). Sri Lanka has recognized as one of the growing automotive markets in the South Asia (SA) region which most of the vehicle's trade through the auto dealers. Vehicle ownership of the consumers in the country has been increased day by day before the pandemic. It was increased by 6% in 2018 while new car registration during that year has been increased by 106% which is abnormal increase (Annexure 1). Import expenditure on motor vehicles also has increased by 66% in the year 2018 compared to 2017. Moreover, government has collected excise duty on motor vehicle imports Rs.204 Bn in 2018 which is 8% growth compared to previous year (Motor Vehicle Industry report 2018). This has demonstrated that automobiles are becoming indispensable in daily life among the Sri Lankans. This thesis is an investigation into consumer perceptions towards automobile product in Sri Lankan market and seeks to find out eco-friendly marketing effects for the different car brands for the purchase of a car. A vast number of environmental issues and social responsibilities have led to customers to think carefully in customers' shopping decisions in the country (CBSL report, 2017). Companies aiming to express their concerns and awareness of the importance of such matters in their marketing activities. In Sri Lanka, for instance, the personal mobility has seen the most dramatic change in the last two decades with the increasing number of households that have access to a private car (Road and Motor Vehicle- (RMV) Annual Report ,2018). Transportation not only requires a high consumption of non-renewable energy resources but also the emissions from vehicles contribute to both local and global environmental problems. For many consumers, a change from conventional car to more environmentally friendly forms of transport imply a conflict between individual short-term interests and social or collective long-term interests (Kurani & Turrentine, 2002). Government has focused on the development strategies to ensure a sustainable development of Sri Lankans automobile industry, (CBSL Annual report, 2017). Moreover, the government's intention was to promote greener, environmentally healthy vehicles to reduce auto emissions that need to engage all operators in the industry. The choices people have made during past 200 years about mode and technologies of transportation have

brought the country extra ordinary global interaction and, in many respects, increased personal freedom. However, all these mobility has become a cost to the society, economy as well as to the environment. Sri Lankan automobile industry has largely ignored these challenges and continued to use the highly technological automobiles with electrical gadgets which consumes more fuel rather than less. These changes have affected more importantly on car market than other types of automobiles due to high usage of cars compared to other automobiles. Environmental pollution across the country has expanded due to the increased number of vehicle usage in Sri Lanka. This has not only been a problem for Sri Lanka but also a worldwide problem (Gunarathne, Alwis, and Alahakoon, 2020). Transportation is contributing considerable amount for the air pollution problem at locally, regionally as well global level. It consumes energies such as fossil fuel, oil and greenhouse gases which are fastest growing source of energy in recently particularly in a developing country. Meantime some developed countries in Europe have started to enforce the use of biofuels to reduce emission and usage of fossil fuels. (Directive, 2009). However, potential for usage of biofuel is limited due to few reasons such as biofuels have not been available at large scale, usage of fertile lands has not been recommended to generate the biofuels at a larger scale. With respect to the above limitations of the energy sources, green car concepts have been increasing within the country, and car manufacturers have been trying to develop that market. With the efficiency improvements due to the technology and price competitiveness in electric cars, there is an increasing demand for these vehicles in the country (environment authority, 2018).

Even the overall air quality situation was good in Sri Lanka, it has been deteriorating due to the high vehicle usage, burning waste, road dusts, industries etc. more than 80% of the industries have located in capital city which is Colombo by contributing to the air quality pollution (de Silva, Yapa, and Vesty, 2020.). Higher demand for the automotive vehicles has been attracted most of the foreign direct investments to manufacture automotive products in the country at large scale. Similarly, one of the main goals of the government also was to attract more foreign currency inflow via automotive industry as mentioned in central bank report 2020. Likewise, government of Sri Lanka also started some initiatives to promote use of Environment friendly green cars by adopting various measures (DK, and Wanninayake, 2015). However, green car market in the country is still in the initial stages and many challenges faced by the auto-dealers and the government. Moreover, consumers have got less knowledge about the environmentally friendly cars and identified as another barrier for the electric car market in the country (Dimo annual report, 2019). In favor of the industry, several factors have helped

such as availability of labour at a reasonable price, geographical location advantage, state support etc. In contrast, one of the main barriers in the automotive market in Sri Lanka was the ongoing economic crisis started during 2018-19. It was one of the worst economic crises occurred since independence 1948. It has led to unprecedented levels of inflation, near weakening of foreign exchange reserves, shortages of medical supplies and an increase in prices of basic commodities. Crisis has started due to the several factors such as tax cuts, money creation, Easter bombings in 2019 and the adverse impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. The subsequent economic hardships made the automotive market bring down considerably (Gunarathne et al., 2021).

Worldwide private motor car ownership has been sharply increasing currently with a little hint that this trend that will be stop in the forceable future (Arunatilake, Inchauste and Lustig, 2017). Transport contributes for roughly 64% of the global oil consumption and worldwide transport energy usage has doubled in the past three decades, mainly due to the enhanced passenger car usage (Energy, Wind. and Outlook, 2015). Increase in private car ownership creates huge risk to the environment as well as health and wellbeing of the people (Ibrahim et al., 2019). Reduce commuting and physical activities caused lot of health problems as well as contribute adversely environment Therefore, it is necessary to reverse this trend of increase of fuel driven car ownership to protect the environment and there is a need of doing research in this area how this can be achieved. As a result, consumers are giving higher priority for eco friendliness in every product which they purchase not only in Sri Lanka but also in many other countries in the world.

When promoting the Electric cars, sales staff of the dealership need to have specific knowledge about the car specifications, express their advantages to customers, environment as well as the economy at large to achieve a sale. But if the sales staff is not powerful and misinformed shoppers they run out of the dealers with empty hands. Therefore, in terms of promotion and sales, there should be competent sales staff and they should express the benefits and sustainable advantages of owning an electric car to the environment and for their personal benefit (Lashari, Ko, and Jang, 2021).

Automobile dealers in Sri Lanka have failed to identify the local market characteristics on what are the mostly influenced factors affecting to the consumer's car financing decision. As the car financing decision is a most valuable decision for the Sri Lankan customers people tend to purchase their car after careful consideration of different choices. Being developing country

digital infrastructure facilities are still developing and there is a need of green marketing technology to promote the eco-friendly cars within the country. Because the people are still more rely on the advertising methods such as billboard, newspapers, television advertisements and other traditional methods (DK and Wanninayake, 2015). There is a higher potential to change the passenger car market due to competition and high technology involvement, because of that automobile manufacturers and the auto dealers required to understand the consumer buying behaviour to take necessary speedy actions (Mhlongo and Mason, 2020). From the supplier point of view, firm should have attractive brand solid green marketing strategy to influence consumer buying decision. Increased efficiency in the use of resources, return on investment, increased sales, development of new markets, improved corporate image, product differentiation, and enhanced competitive advantage are examples of several benefits that firms can get when having sound marketing strategy with attractive branding into business activities (Bhat, 1993; Fierman, 1991; Peattie, 1992; Miles & Munilla, 1993; Shrivastava et al., 1998; Berry & Rondinelli, 1998; Henriques & Sadorsky, 1999; Kolk, 2003) But to obtain such benefits, appropriate strategies are necessary. There is need of investigation and identification of eco-friendly marketing which benefits to the car dealers to promote their brands which influence the purchase intention. Consequently, there is a need of analysing brand preference, evaluating company's green marketing strategy and implementing proper advertising and sales strategies to boost the sales. There is a potentiality to start up electric car companies in the country as it is lacking due to the unavailability of resources such as infrastructure facilities, capital investment etc. But as the government has been invited to new foreign investors to invest in the country, there is a need of investigating the eco-friendly car market sustainability to attract new investors and organisations have huge responsibility towards the promoting green marketing strategies for the betterment of the car market in Sri Lanka. This research will investigate how brand image will influence the purchase decision of a car and how it will affect to maximise sellers return as a part of green marketing strategy.

In the year 2021, the electronic items wastage has increased worldwide compared to few years before as discussed by Nicholas, Papparoidamis and Huong ,2018. It has caused in drastic environmental challenges and incurred serious problems than the other various wastages. Similar problem occurred in the country Sri Lanka which government hardly finding solution to manage the wastage. When people transferring to electric cars from the conventional cars countries have faced for this issue and need immediate actions on that (Sovacool, and Hirsh, 2009) As such there is a need of promoting green cars withing the country through providing

more knowledge about waste management and benefit of eco-friendly cars and this could be achieved through solid green marketing strategy which influence purchase of green cars.

Consumption and the production of the cars have become significant in economically, environmentally as well as politically around the globe in terms of the trade. Car industry has contributed to enhance the Gross Domestic Production (GDP) in countries which produce and sell the cars while affecting to the balance of payment, employment and income level, economic growth and as a valuable investment. Global passenger car market has expanded over the past decade rapidly making human life much better and efficient. This research will be looked at economical and environment aspects of the Sri Lankan car industry which has relatively neglected in the academic literature. In addition to the economic and environment importance of distributing, car has made convenient for the lifestyle providing a solution for the human's transportation problems. While majority use passenger cars for their basic transportation, some other people buy cars to show off their prestige and status. (Sunday Times, 2019).

1.3 Research Aim

The aim of this research study is to analyse and evaluate Mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on car purchasing intention Sri Lanka

1.4 Research Questions

- How does the environmental awareness affect to purchase intention?
- How does the perceived value affect to purchase intention?
- How does the green trust affect to purchase intention?
- How is brand image mediating between eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka?
- What green marketing strategies are used by car dealer companies in the Sri Lanka?

1.5 Research Objectives

- To determine the Environmental awareness among the people, affect to purchasing intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka

- To determine the green perceived is having a significant relationship with purchasing intention of cars in Sri Lanka.
- To determine the influence of green trust in marketing strategies for the purchasing intention of cars.
- To determine mediation of Brand Image on car purchase intention
- To identify the green marketing strategies used by car dealer companies in SL.

1.6 Significance of the Study

Given that the Sri Lankan car industry is the one of largest contributor to the country's GDP among all other industries it is important firms perform well and attract more customers for the development of the industry (CBSL report 2020). As a vulnerable country to environment pollution there is a need of investigation of environmental awareness among the people in Sri Lanka in terms of motor car purchase. Further, fertilization of ideas will also help to share best practices and develop guidelines that can be used by managers to distinguish their products and services and achieve sustainable growth. This understanding has the potential to support the car industry in Sri Lanka and create an opportunity for effective distinguished tribal marketing strategies with the intention of creating sustainable growth amongst car dealer companies. This study will provide thorough knowledge for the automotive dealers, manufacturers, and other stakeholders to seek any information about car purchase behaviour in Sri Lanka.

1.7 Scope of the Study

This study focuses on different green marketing strategies which help the car market in Sri Lanka and finding its effects for the purchase intention among Sri Lankan people to achieve environmental protection. The increase in environmental issues around the world have been affected to select the topic and as a result changing customer preference and taste, escalated competition in the car industry is becoming difficult to perform well (Kotabe, and Helsen, 2022). Car industry has affected by different challenges especially due to the growing environmental issues. Implementation of different marketing strategies to promote green car concept is essential and prove to be advantage for the stakeholders (Moravcikova et al., 2017). Researcher has basically undertaken this study to identify and analyse eco-friendly behaviour of marketers and consumers through the green marketing strategies and find the purchase intention behaviour under car market in Sri Lanka. Several car brands available in Sri Lanka have been considered the eco-friendliness to prevent environmental pollution and there is a

mutual responsibility of consumers as well as car dealers to protect environment through their behaviour. Green marketing strategy has taken priority to influence the consumer purchase intention of the car and it has analysed through this study in terms of car market in Sri Lanka.

1.8 Definitions of Key Terms

Purchase Intention - Purchase intention is the consumer's willingness to purchase a given product at a certain time or situation (Oliver, and Lee, 2010). In this study, purchase intention is viewed as the preference of purchase of green car brand, an act mediated by the willingness of brand image.

Green Marketing – This is referring to general marketing concept wherein the production, marketing consumption and disposal of products and services happen in a manner that is less damaging to the environment with growing consciousness about global warming, non-biodegradable solid waste, harmful impact of pollutants etc., both marketers and consumers are becoming increasingly sensitive to the need for switch in to green products and services (Mishra, and Sharma,2010).

Brand Image – This is defined as “customer perceptions about a brand as reflected by the brand association held in consumer memory”. These associations are anything linked in customer memory to a brand (Aaker, 1991).

Green Trust- this is defined as a willingness to depend on a product, service, or brand based on the belief or anticipation resulting from its credibility, goodwill, and ability about its environmental performance (Chen 2010).

Perceived Quality - This is conceptualised as the consumer's intelligence about a products' overall excellence or superiority and perceived quality is also considered to be a comparison between actual performance of the brand and the consumers' expectation (Calvo-Porrá, and Lévy-Mangin, 2017).

1.9 Methodological Discussion

A deductive approach has been adopted in this study. The study was pitched towards testing the relationship between variables, and this is consistent with a deductive approach which involves the testing of a theory. Thus, from existing statistics a hypothesis or a series of reasons are deduced. It is because of a deductive approach that the researcher managed to determine the relationship between eco-friendly marketing and purchase intention. This utilised primary data sets and adopted a survey and empirical research design (Rauniar et al., 2014). Researcher conducts the study based on both qualitative and quantitative data which is mixed methods. Comparative analysis of both qualitative and quantitative data and findings from them help researcher to analyse behaviour and environmental awareness of the people and companies' green marketing strategy in the car industry of Sri Lanka. Based on the respondent's responses researcher was able to interpret the data to meet the study purpose. Survey questionnaires were distributed to consumers and car dealers of some car brands while interviews were conducted for the same category of respondents. Thus, the data was primarily quantitative and qualitative. The population was the Sri Lankan car dealers and consumers which has interest on car brands. The study adopted a probabilistic sampling method. This helped to reach those respondents who were associated with the UK fashion industry and were aware of shopping apparels from various outlets or online and expressed an interest to participate in the study on a voluntary basis.

The sample size selected for this study was 384 respondents. The sample was drawn from both online platforms and offline platforms. Most importantly data was analysed using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) to have better outcome. In a similar manner, qualitative data analysed using thematic analysis to by identifying most critical responses from the participants.

1.10 Chapters/ Structure of the Thesis

Figure 1: Structure of thesis

Chapter 1: This chapter discusses the background to the study. It also defines the problem statement, research questions and objectives. The chapter provides an overview of the thesis.

Chapter 2: This chapter critically reviews literature encompassing environmental awareness, green marketing strategies, purchase intention, branding, and other associated concepts. It also recognizes gaps in knowledge and positions the study.

Chapter 3: This chapter explains the current situation and issues relating to the car industry in Sri Lanka. Company reports, industry reports and government reports were the main sources for this chapter and it helps to understand the research problem due to the detail information.

Chapter 4: This chapter considers the methodology of the study. Here, it concentrates on outlining and justifying the research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, sampling, and data analysis issues. Data collection techniques explained and justified in this section and the characteristics of the respondents also discuss.

Chapter 5: This chapter shows a detailed examination of the collected data sets. Firstly, it concentrates about the primary data sets collected and analysis techniques, and descriptive

techniques to recognize the patterns in the collected data sets. For the clear understanding of problem this section was helped. Secondly this chapter focuses on a detailed analysis of the primary data sets using thematic analysis for the qualitative part of the study.

Chapter 6: This chapter discusses the results presented in chapter 5, in combination with the literature reviewed in Chapter 2. Understandings acquired from Chapter 5 are evaluated with insights that were found from Chapter 2 . This helped to establish a gap for the study contribution, thereby furthering understanding in terms of knowledge, and practical managerial contribution.

Chapter 7: This chapter concludes the study, reviews the study objectives considering the findings, and discusses the contributions of the study. The study also makes recommendations drawn from the findings and gaps in knowledge.

1.11 Chapter Summary

Overall, of research topic has been outlined in this chapter of study. This chapter has presented the research aims, questions, and objectives and research background as been discussed. Further a short description on the methodology has been summarized, with the significance and the scope of the research. The next chapter critically reviews the appropriate body of academic literature.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction to Literature Review

This chapter analyses and evaluate related literature review and theories specific to this study. Critical evaluation done for the environmental awareness, green marketing strategy, green perceived value, green trust, purchase intention and brand image. It eventually developed conceptual framework which is crucial and shows interconnection between variables to be tested via this research. This is an academic insight of which researcher could apply most suitable information to the context of the study.

2.2 Environmental Awareness and Corporations

Most important consideration is the environmental impact from the automobiles, and this is a concerning factor in the present research activity (Subhani, et al., 2022). Present technology developments are focusing more on the eco-friendly nature of the cars and more importantly, there are situations that manage the outcomes in making the better car delivery for the environment which makes the less impact and to reduce the carbon impact for the atmosphere (Jayalath & Wedasinghe, 2020). These actions are encouraging the people to use low carbon emission vehicles, and this is mostly due to the government tax policies and the other punishing methods for the over usage and over application of the carbon emissions than provided.

In developed countries, customers are more conscious about sustainability and like to choose eco-friendly products. Therefore, many customers think that companies should take actions to develop the environment (Yamak et al., 2014). Recently there is a trend in the automotive industry to develop eco-friendly vehicles and huge investments have been made to make environmentally friendly vehicles. Motor cars have taken priority over other vehicles as consumers mostly use them over other vehicles. The automotive industry is one of the popular industries which causes environmental pollution and cars have a considerable impact throughout the product life cycle (Orsato and Wells, 2017). Continuous growth in the industry has influenced the increasing use of cars globally as well as the growing demand in developing countries. This has ultimately increased the CO₂ emission making a harmful impact to the environment. However, manufacturers have shown their awareness of environmental impact, environmental regulations resulted in higher demand for environmentally less destructive cars.

This has also led to competitive advantage over other car manufacturers who do not consider environment friendliness (Davila et al., 2007; Till et al., 2009). Due to rapid growth in the global population, growing demand has occurred for transportation. Recently the choice of environmental practices or changes in the way that processes and products are designed to make them less harmful to the environment has been a trend in business management (González-Benito et al, 2008). Strategies that prioritize the implementation of eco-friendly practices are linked to the firm's perception of current environmental pressure from media, regulatory institutions, financial institutions, suppliers, competitors, etc. The ability of firms to scan the external business environment to identify threats and opportunities and its sensitivity to respond to such external pressure are characteristics of market-oriented firms (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990). Thus, market orientation should be a driving force to set the cultural and operational bases for increased awareness and committed reactions to the current environmental trends.

As per Toshiba's corporate communications director, consumers concentrate on buying more environmentally friendly products and brands which are less harmful to the planet (Repole, 2019). In contrast to that, as per the major motor car manufacturers have pointed out that cost is too high for the consumers in comparison with conventional automobiles. Manufacturers who make environmentally friendly cars have to offer a competitive price for cars with more green options. Moreover, it has suggested that support from the government need to be enhanced by giving tax credits, implementing friendly legislations on behalf of eco-friendly car manufacturers/consumers, and increasing penalties for polluters (Pandey and Kaushik, 2012).

Another study has been carried out to check the factors affecting consumer's green product purchase in India as there has been a growing awareness in green awareness in developing countries. This has been done in southwestern India with 192 respondents and using 19 variables to check the level of influence to purchase green products (Pandey and Kaushik 2012). The study has pointed out several identifications and these are funding (income, government funding, credit schemes), credibility (Quality certification by government) and distribution network (easy product availability, quality) which has mainly influenced the consumers green product purchase. The study has found that credibility was most important factor which influenced to buy green products. The study also highlighted that if organizations marketing convinced that green product purchase has been considered as an investment,

consumers tend to purchase more green products. Moreover, it has found out that company's marketing of the green products should create attractive credit schemes for green product consumers to improve green product consumption and revenue. Additionally, the study emphasized that if there was easy availability of quality green products it would impact positively consumer's green product purchase decisions (Pandey and Kaushik 2012). Therefore, there is a requirement for analysing green products for the different products to have a proper understanding of how companies and people react in towards the green products.

Furthermore, sustainable development considered as the growth which meets the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs as discussed by Verma, 2019. This relates to the concept of environmentally friendly cars in this research. However, this conflicts with the expectations of consumers and sustainability. Because most of the consumers will choose a car to satisfy their needs without considering the environment (Gabriel and Lang, 2006). Moreover, the eco-friendly factors affect in various ways in different markets, depending on culture of countries and the economic condition, therefore those market behaviours may differ from each other (Chu et al., 2019). In the past there were many researchers conducted for the developed markets and found that those countries have adopted eco-friendly products significantly more than developing countries. Hence there is a need for investigation of eco-friendly motor cars in such countries as there is a huge potential in those markets (Lee et al., 2021). As a result of both pressure of resource reduction and environmental changes, the electrical vehicle concept also has taken most priority in the current automotive industry (Tu, and Yang, 2019). A study has taken to investigate the factors affecting to acceptance of the electric vehicles using seven hypotheses. This has based on the three key theories such as Theory of planned behaviour (TPB), Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT) which explained how people adopted to innovations and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) explains the how external factors affect the internal attitudes, behaviour etc. It has mainly had a discussion of attitudes and behaviour about the consumers with reference to purchase of electric vehicles. Study has conducted in coastal areas of China using 300 valid responses have collected. It was found that most of the dimensions have an impact on consumers' behavioural intention of purchasing electric vehicles and consumers from their surroundings also have a great impact on consumers' intention to purchase electric vehicles. Additionally personal innovativeness has had a negative impact, which shown that when consumers think they have no better understanding of electric vehicles than others around them, they will not prioritize electric vehicles. Above study has focused on consumer, there is a requirement of investigation

of green perspectives and green marketing concepts to evaluate the industry perspective. As such current research is in a focus of evaluating green marketing among the different brands.

Car manufacturers are always considered to be the main polluters and due to that reason, they plan numerous green product developments. They must behave as green producers, accept green alternatives when they purchase green resources, maintain green production and logistics and save natural resources at all the time. Vast number of cars exhale dangerous substances worldwide, and the car industry is also responsible for the environmental pollution. Ecological burden has been incurred in raw material extraction, production of parts, energy based producing etc. Disposal of old used cars and recycling them were the best method to reduce environmental pollution (Sakris et., all 2010). In Europe regulations have already been exposed to encourage clean and sustainable travel by focusing on commercial vehicle emission standards, smart charging, new tech, and usage of alternative fuel (Wu et al., 2017). Therefore, it is important to develop low-carbon, energy-savings, intelligent electrical vehicles to reduce environmental impact. Although the production of electric cars has been increasing around the world, the market presence of them was very low compared to other cars. Therefore, it is necessary to assess which factors will affect the purchase intention of consumers for cars. Godlevskaja et al., 2011 mentioned that the electric cars are sustainable compared to the conventional car to consumers. Due to its innovative features, service components are the factors which influence the decision to purchase cars. Past literature has found that when comparing environmental externalities from gasoline cars and electric cars, electrical vehicles generate negative externalities than gasoline cars (Yates et al., 2016). Jui-Che Tu and Chun Yang, 2019 have discovered that some of the governments have announced that they are going to ban internal combustion engine cars which influence the development of electric cars. As a result, most states have taken actions to promote electric vehicles through sending clear guidance to vehicle manufacturers and stakeholders, by increasing their future policies.

Figure 2: Announced sales bans for Internal Combustion Engine (ICE) vehicles.

Additionally, as discovered in that study, major car manufacturers also have announced that they are going to change the production of electrical cars in larger quantities over other cars. By proving that some suppliers also have announced that they are going to manufacture only hybrid and electric cars and some of them are going to change the production of electric cars in near future which has proven that there are environmentally friendly which will positively affect to the car purchase behaviour in the future (Jui-Che Tu and Chun Yang 2019). Another study has been found out that Indian consumers were the most likely to buy more electric cars and thereafter Chinese consumers due to the reasons of avoidance of pollution and protection of the environment. Moreover, consumers with high income, high social status, awareness of the environment and high living conditions are more likely to purchase electric cars. In contrast, when people have no more understanding about the electrical vehicles than other vehicles, they don't tend to buy electrical vehicles and are more likely to purchase traditional vehicles (Heffner et al., 2007). Similarly, even if all the private cars were fully electric, there are additional external factors which consumers face due to the parking space problems, traffic jams with the increase of urbanization.

Another study has investigated the population segment consisting of women, older adults, ethnic minorities, and urban residents are more concern about the climate change and think about environment before they make purchase decision of a car which challenged the findings which discovered more educated and rich people are concerned with more environmental factors (Samuel et al.,2019). When reviewing the literature on the eco friendliness effect on car purchase decisions, we have come a crossed that the environmental changes and the car buyers' behaviours. Thogersen, 2006 have found that people who are concerned about climate change and prefer to adjust their behaviour, accordingly, were thinking more about the environment when they make car purchasing decisions. This trend should be encouraged further, especially

in the car industry to protect future environment. Similarly, Lynn (2014) has investigated that people who are eco-friendly at home also tend to buy more eco-friendly items. Higher repetition of pro-environmental consumer behaviours at home (Eg: using low energy bulbs and switching off unnecessary lights) and shopping behaviours such as purchasing recyclable products relate to the purchase consideration in the car buying decisions. However, this pattern couldn't always be observed as discussed by S Chng Chong Wei, 2017. In contrast, even consumers use car sharing and taking less flights by thinking at the environment, when it comes to their day today life, they tend to use public transport or cars as convenient modes whereby people place less prominence to environmental factors in car purchasing decision. Because consumers have treated future environmental impact from cars are less important than pro-environmental travel behaviours as explained in the above (Schultz et al., 2017).

Moreover, past literature has found that cultural differences between countries have affected the consumer's car purchasing behaviour in various ways. Even the advocates believed that collective effort to achieve global sustainability, it is an important task to identify these differences based on individual cultures. As such there are differences between Asian countries and western countries thinking about the environment. While Asian people think that protecting the environment is a tradition and must do it as they respect their parents, Western world people think that environmental values are related with altruistic values which concern others (Aoyagi-Usui et al., (2003). Another behaviour recognized by Laroche et al., 2001 identified that consumers avoid the companies who pollute the environment and do not use eco-friendly methods to produce packaging in their purchase decision. As such people tend to find out the information about a company whether it positively or negatively contributes to the environment before they decide to purchase a car. Moreover, people who have higher interest in green products are attracted to higher involvement in green products due to the social values but not related to their own environmental values. Customers who buy hybrid cars, which are more eco-friendly, think that it save their money in future and protect their prestige due to the higher price paid for hybrid cars (Jason and Lee, 2010).

CO₂ emission has also influenced the decision to purchase of cars among the consumers which was found by Gaker et al.,2013. Because it is difficult to interpret CO₂ information in mass media which general consumers cannot understand properly unless the customer is an environmentalist. In contrast, some researchers have analysed the yearly effect of CO₂ emission on usage of cars in some regions and reduced the mental burden on humans.

Some studies have found that cyclists and bus passengers are more vulnerable to traffic-related air-pollution than car drivers due to closed windows in cars. Additionally, the usage of electric cars offers strategic opportunities for efficient decrease in road pollution and thereby increase road-user safety and environmental sustainability (Timo et al., 2017).

Some researchers have pointed out that increasing demand from the stakeholders to protect the social and environment has become a responsibility of corporations to protect them. Therefore, they have taken some strategies to reduce harm by producing and distributing motor cars. As a result, they have taken steps to protect by producing electric cars which minimize greenhouse gas emission. Moreover, as an emerging business model they have introduced a concept of selling mobility instead of selling cars which was discussed by Firnkorn and Muller, 2012. As an example, they have introduced a large-scale car-sharing system and car2go system as a strategic business model which reduces environmental harm (Firnkorn and Müller, 2012). This has led to reducing the traffic-related problems as well as reducing private vehicle usage in urban areas. This has negatively affected the purchasing of private cars in developed countries such as the USA, UK, Germany etc. (Kynaston, 2011). In terms of implementing these strategies, respective governments have a responsibility to supply related infrastructure facilities such as building parking spaces and charging places for electric cars etc. One shared car has been able to replace 24 private cars in most populated cities and has reduced some land consumption which has positively affected the environment as they were using electric cars for these strategies. Thus, there is an opportunity to share fixed costs of electric cars among users rather than spending by one person to own their own private cars and that was investigated by Firnkorn and Müller, 2012. However, as per them that system had to be implemented with the help of policy makers of respective countries and had a question as to whether all the car passengers would be willing to use these methods as there are some areas which hasn't been investigated by researchers such as how these system cope with location of the people who live and their job locations etc. Consequently, selling mobility instead of selling cars need further investigation by experts to get the maximum benefit from it (Firnkorn and Müller, 2012). Therefore, there is a need of meditation of marketing to protect the environment by adopting to less harmful practices. Above study has focused on consumer, there is a requirement of investigation of eco-friendly perspectives and green marketing concepts to evaluate the consumer purchase habits. As such current research is in a focus of evaluating green marketing concepts which influence the consumer.

Some advocates found that driving habits also result in negative environmental impact by car owners. Eco-driving strategies have been investigated to improve fuel-efficiency and reduce environmental harm from greenhouse gas production generated in the transport sector. The main area of this process was to reduce the fuel wastage of cars in different ways. As discussed by R. Massound 2019, encouraging to drive by avoiding the brakes, selecting smooth routes (eg: choosing smooth road surface, avoiding traffic), making one trip to avoid multiple travels to make use of the warm engine, transporting more people in one car by sharing car cost with each other are a few suggested options. Moreover, eco-driving rules have been suggested to avoid high fuel consumption and reduce the environmental damage; accelerate smoothly, maintain similar speed level in the traffic flow, stop the engine when there is a long stop etc. Even accelerating excessively to make it run faster will make less economy level of fuel and increase environmental pollution.

Additionally, providing eco driving training to the company employees has also positively contributed to the environment and eco driving coaching has avoided the high fuel consumption as discovered by seven European union countries. He also investigated that there is a possibility of saving fuel regardless of technological developments when drivers follow fuel economical driving styles. This is related with the car purchase and maintenance decisions as eco-driving has a relationship with the environmental impact. Another aspect of environmental impact is the car manufacturing year as discussed by Massound 2019. He found out that if the car construction year is more recent, it is more fuel-efficient than old ones. If a customer buys a car with a gasoline engine, it increases the fuel economy and will influence them to buy those cars more than high fuel consumption cars and it less harmful for the environment than a car with low fuel emission. These findings have resulted to impact company's marketing decisions of the green products and the purchase intention of the consumers which is going to study in this research.

2.3 Green Marketing Introduction

Green marketing concept identified as marketing products or services without making harming to the environment (American Marketing Association ,1975). However, green marketing also explained as the process of selling products and/or services based on their environmental benefits (ICBM 2018). As per these definitions companies need to think about environmental friendliness while satisfy customer needs through the products which offer. Moreover, green marketing is more than reduction of environmental harm which seeks consumption of products which create sustainable development. (Jayathilaka, 2018).

Green marketing also defined as all activities created to generate and support exchanges purposes to satisfy people needs and wants with a minimal detrimental impact on the natural environment (Pavan et al, 2010). Green marketing Eco-friendly concepts has emerged in late 1980 and earlier 1990. Since then, researchers have embarked upon different waves supported by a growing consumer interest in green products and a pronounced willingness to pay for green features (Laroche et all, 2001). In contrast, claims that consumers preferred to pay more for green products was not clear since the green demand in the 90's had increased only very little and this was evidenced in Mintel's reports published in 1995 (Mintle,1995). In this perspective, some researchers have agreed and suggested that the opinions of consumers do not appear to translate into changes in purchasing behaviour (Carrigan & Attala, 2001). That is, there appears to be a gap between what consumers say about the importance of green products or ethical issues and what they do when purchasing products.

Stone and Wakefield (2000) made a link between market orientation and environmental practices and adapt the market orientation concept to an "eco-oriented" one, which refers to organization that generates, discloses, and responds to environmental information. Impressive pollution and its consequences for human health, scarcity of freshwater and raw material, and global warming are among others climate challenges that demand a response from society. In some way, all these environmental impacts have a great influence on how companies manage their business, and therefore, they are also a driver to innovate eco-friendly products (Jeong, et all, 2014). To develop green products as well as to address environmental awareness firms need to create a successful strategy. Strategic planning requires simple, consistent, and long-term firms' goals, a deep understanding of the competitive environment as well as realistic objectives that are aligned with the firm's resources and capabilities (Grant, 2005). Oslon, 2008

has found out that creating a green strategy has no different and clear vision and objectives have been useful to help managers in making better decisions. According to Olson (2008), a green or environmental strategy should lead to a common culture of awareness and actions that encourage initiatives to benefit the planet and at the same time add attractive value propositions to the firm. Similarly, an attractive value proposition has been understood here as the development of new technologies or initiatives that can reduce cost and increase performance. Solar panels, electric cars, hydrogen vehicle conversions, recycling and rainwater collection are examples of alternative Eco-friendly technologies that are cost effective. The first step that firms should take when implementing an environmental strategy is to increase green awareness and actions as corporate culture. To do this, they should include environmental issues as part of their training curriculum that focus on organizations' environmental goals. In that manner there is a requirement for the companies around the world to act necessarily to protect the environment. Olson (2008) highlighted the importance of organizations in developing practices that cultivate a common culture of environmental consciousness to support its green strategy. That study has found that one important aspect of responsible environmental practices was that it has increased corporate reputation. Fombrun (1996) proposed that a corporation's reputation is associated with credibility; trustworthiness; and responsibility. Firms producing superior quality products, using credible advertising, acting in a socially and environmentally responsible manner and having a history of examples in which their obligations meet various stakeholder interests tend to create reputational advantage (Miles & Covin, 2000). As per the above literature, most companies preferred to produce Eco-friendly goods to enhance their reputation and attract potential customers. In a study conducted in India to analyse the green marketing has found that organisations used their green practices through products, processes and by communicating that they have increased the business performance and it is a responsibility of both consumers and companies. This was conducted based using 168 respondents and measured the level of green marketing practices (Mayakkannan, 2019).

Another research carried out by Singh and Pandey, 2012 has investigated that organizational level attributes such as eco-friendly of production processes and systems have been affected and it is crucial to influence the consumers and convey that company's genuineness. As it found that consumer wanted green products from green firms and have identified that firm-level processes and systems helped to promote corporate image. Transparent green marketing practices have been attracted consumers to purchase their products. Customer segmentation has been identified as critical factor in the ecological marketing which companies should

focused on to influence the potential customer to achieve higher customer base. Understanding of the current customer base with their attitude has been beneficial to decide investment on green marketing. Decision was made based on customers' likelihood of turning to purchase green products. Moreover, selecting which strategy to follow has depended up on the company's experience, capabilities, and level of the competition. Competitor analysis also has been critical when deciding the green marketing strategy to increase purchase intention. Additionally, that study has found that employee participation of providing green ideas within the corporate culture to have success green marketing strategy. Educating consumers through the knowledgeable sales team also has suggested for customers to try a new green product. Further, it has investigated that basic customer needs which expected from a product should be given a priority and thereafter necessity of the basic ecological attributes of the product. Companies should be mindful about the risk of integrating green marketing such as huge investment to implementation of green marketing strategy, anticipated compliance issues and potential losing of green trust due to next environmental issues etc (Ginsberg, and Bloom, 2004).

Consumers are these days more conscious about various shopping attitudes and purchases. People think about living long life and consider about the planet. As a result, they have contributed to protect the environment maximum even their shopping and purchasing behaviours. Consumers have turned to purchase eco-friendly products and spent higher amount of money to those and this behaviour towards the environment has developed green marketing concept (Ansar, 2013). In a research factor affecting to purchasing and influence of green marketing has been discussed using electronic goods. The study has analysed socio demographic variables, eco-friendly advertisements ecological packaging in Karachchi, Pakistan using 384 population. It has concluded that some socio demographic variables are not affecting to purchase intention even the previous researchers have found that there was an effect of those to purchase intention. Also, green marketing (advertising) has positive relationship with the price and consumers have purchased the electronic goods due to the eco-friendly nature. But some of the ecological packaging has negative correlation with the purchase intention (Ansar, 2013).

2.4 Importance of Green Marketing

Green marketing has developed as part of the growing process of the marketing discipline. The application of marketing tools has impacted on satisfaction levels of different organizations. Companies have actively pursued green marketing methods with the intention of attracting and holding customers, as well as building a good reputation for their brands (Cronin et al., 2011). Car dealers have grabbed upon the green marketing philosophies to attract consumers. Due to overrun marketing strategies some organizations have violated environmental legislations which could cause fines and punishments. As a result, it turned to have a harmful reputation of companies in the industry. Consequently, there is essential requirement for organizations to pursue green marketing with legitimate interest, rather than just as a practice to acquire consumers. This is in need for the car sellers to have a sustainable development which covered all three aspects environmental protection, social responsibilities, economic practices (Colucci et al., 2020). In contrast, a study has found out that green brands have rejected due to the lack of awareness among the consumers, and it has not been influences customers properly. Therefore, firms have a huge responsibility to provide goods to their customers with the understanding of accountability of satisfying their needs while protecting environment (Haws et al. (2010), Kai et al. (2013) Thogersen et al. (2012), Yang et al. (2015). For the purpose of reduction of environmental pollution and the increase the revenues have been identified as balanced method of use of green marketing concept by multi-national corporations such as Toyota (Yan and Yazdanifard, 2014). Toyota has produced Prius which offered several desirable benefits for consumers and the natural environment (Halbright & Dunn, 2010). Prius has had an environmental engine which includes emission-reducing fuel, so it has decreased the emission of carbon dioxide and nitrogen dioxide into the air; lower emissions has been resulted in to a positive impact on the environment, lowering the pollution emitted in to the environment. When considerable number of people were to buy a Prius, it affected to have a large impact on global warming, but the sale of one of these cars has not been solved the problem as mentioned by May, Cheney, & Roper, 2007. When the fuel price increasing, Toyota produced Prius has been saved fuel cost which has been identified as positive factor. As such people who have strong environmental concerns, has resulted to have ecologically conscious buying behaviour and use of a hybrid cars (Balderjahn, 1988). Researcher has concluded that Prius brand satisfied the demand of the consumers for an eco-friendly product in such a manner. Therefore, the customers have expressed great satisfaction towards the eco-friendly product

which has built up a positive judgment towards Toyota Corporation has trusted the brand due to the higher reliability of Toyota's products.

2.5 Online Advertising

Study conducted in China has been identified that most of the branded products have not sold for the utility value rather have represented the emotions such as love, friendship, youth, family etc. The kindness of natural pictures in the auto-ads have achieved via the process of de-contextualization, with images of real natural environment being replaced. These fantastic scenarios have effortlessly incorporated into the close-ups showing the promoted car models. Through the visual narrative of nature itself has been identified and reconfigured as a primary source of commodity need through the advertisements showing consumer experiences of automobiles as an added value. Chen, 2016 has found that those kind of green marketing through advertising has convinced the customers to purchase personal cars. Another study carried out in India, has been identified three different measures in green advertising such as advertising must educate consumers about environment, it should convey the people that company has changed its procedures and manufacturing to promote environmental friendly lifestyle and convey the message of company's responsibility of protecting environment through the advertising (Mishra, and Sharma, 2010).

2.6 Theories of Purchasing Intention

2.6.1 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

There are linkages between the beliefs and the behaviours that is making proper reactions and this link is knowing and explaining in the theory of planned behaviour (Steinmetz, et al., 2016). There are three components that are discussing in this theory and these three components are the attitude, subjective norm, and the perceived behavioural control. TPB assumes that consumer behaviour is depending on people's willingness or intention to act. Intention or the willingness depending on the consumer's attitudes for behaviour, subjective and social norms and the perceived control of their own behaviour. Following figure gives the explanation of these connections in a clear manner (Rich, et al., 2015; Yuriev, et al., 2020).

Figure 0-3: Theory of Planned Behaviour

Understanding each of the stage in this theory comes as important which is deciding the behaviour of the applications in a clear level. Further, all the types of behaviours that the individuals are having in understanding the identifications in a clear level has been explaining in this section in a most effective manner (Steinmetz, et al., 2016). Abraham and Sheeran (2003) review that the TPB is a model which explains the relationships between cognitive experiences of human behaviour, it can be handled easily by offer of guidelines, it is economical and what is more, it is supported by empirical research. TPB has identified as the most dominant model of attitude-behaviour relations as discussed by Armitage, Christian and Abrams, 2003. Hence, due to the characteristics of the TPB as a high authenticity, a good predictive accuracy and as the theory strongly is supported by empirical research within the current research the model has used to investigate this research and purchase decision making process is to be developed according to the TPB.

2.6.2 Theory of Reasoned Actions (TRA)

This is another important theory that is explaining the consumer behavior that they are taking a pre-existing experience to their buying pattern (Otieno, et al., 2016). It is coming as important and needed to manage these actions and to manage the outcomes in understanding the necessary actions which the consumer is thinking as per the experiences taken into consideration on the level of the prior experiences (Yzer, 2017). The consumer is needed to have a reason to believe and as per this reason the actions are taking place. Further, this theory

is very important to manage the outcome in making better decisions in several actions to manage the outcomes in effective level (Xiao, 2020). Several previous studies carried out have found that relationship of the attitude and the behaviour relatively low and some theorists proposed eliminating attitude as a factor underlying behaviour. They have concluded that it is critical to have a high degree of correspondence between measures of attitude, norm, perceived control, intention, and behaviour in terms of action, target, context, and time (Montano and Kasprzyk, 2015). They have found that change of any of the factors results in various behaviour being explained.

2.7 Conceptual Model Development

2.7.1 Purchasing Intention

Purchase intention could be identified as one of the most common terms used in businesses and customers are main concern of any business. Intention of buyer to purchase a specific product is referred as the purchase intention (Guo et al., 2018). Purchasing is the process of buying the products or the services by the customer. It is coming as important and the purchasing is the final act of the customer before making the necessary decision on the outcome (Rahim, et al., 2016). Along with this identification, it is coming as very important and needed to manage the outcomes in most effective manner to deliver the better deliveries in managing the product or the service delivery actions (Xu, et al., 2018). Along with this, it comes as important and needed in making the developments in managing the successful product purchasing that comes as important and needed for the better delivery. Another important identification can be recorded as the idea for the purchasing that is stimulated by several factors that is counted as important for the organizational developments to make the necessary outcomes in effective level (Zhuang, et al., 2021). As purchase intention is a crucial aspect of business, business managers evaluate the purchase intention of potential customers in order to initiate a well-structured business strategy which comprises all product development related consequences as well as market predictions of the product.

The idea of the purchasing is coming as very important and needed before the purchasing in undertaking. Intention on purchasing is the idea on the purchasing. This is caused and resulted

due to many factors (Sheng, et al., 2019). This is the willingness of the customer to purchase and it comes as very important and needed to make these outcomes and the necessary actions in most effective level (Sakar, et al., 2019). Most importantly, purchasing intention is coming as critical to make the final decisions on purchasing. This is one of the most important facts in marketing where the marketing is needed to be done in order to increase the intention on purchasing and not to deviate the customer but to attract the customer (Pucci, et al., 2019).

Intent marketing has been undertaken in order to create the intentions on the purchasing and this intention on marketing is recorded as important in managing the outcomes in most successful level. Most importantly, these intentions have been marketed by the marketers in making better deliveries in the identifications (Rahim, et al., 2016) and further, it is coming as important and needed to make the necessary outcomes to a better marketing management application which is necessary in the developing. Among all these applications, understanding the intentions and the factors affecting these intentions are necessary to learn (Sheng, et al., 2019). There are five main factors that can be impacted on the purchasing intention and these factors are as follows.

1. Stimulus – a cue that makes the buyer feel the need of the product or the service.
2. Outcome expectation – the needed results of the product and service consumption
3. Aspirational value – the aspiration gained by the user.
4. Recommendations – trustworthiness
5. Emotional association – emotionally associated with the product.

These five applications are needed in understanding and it is highly needed to understand these applications in making the successful management actions to the better delivery.

To build strong relationship between consumer and the brand there should be a positive interconnection among each factor of the organization which influence the purchase intention of consumer dedication towards brand at greater level. This also helps organizational success efficiently (Carroll and Ahuvia, 2016).

Purchase intention has been depended up on the results which is anticipated by a consumer from that product or service. If the consumer think that product or service is extraordinary and matches with their requirement, it is likely to purchase that product/service. Sometimes

consumers purchase products and services based on the recommendations of the trusted people and this could be identified as strong influential factor. Therefore consumers have stress free mind after buying those products which strengthens their purchase intention.

Purchase intention for a car is not essential as it is not necessity good, and preference is based up on the individual's aspiration. In the case of unavailability or shortage of public transport it is a necessity good rather buying luxury car. The person is likely to develop an emotional connotation with the brand and refuses to let go of it even if new and cheaper competitors branded products become popular among the lots. Additionally, sometimes customers are triggered by certain factors that affect their purchase intentions (Zhang, and Kim, 2013). Research conducted for the recognition and analysis of influential factors affected to purchase intention of certain brand in India, few factors which influence purchase intention of customer were identified such as, brand name, product quality, product packaging, product price, and product advertising as per the literature review. Data collected were analysed and come up with the conclusion that few factors including advertising, quality and brand name were significantly affect for the purchase intention but not the price and product packaging. It was concluded that the brand should investing on advertising should be done and to upgrade the brand name and product quality in order to gain competitive advantage by making positive impact on the purchase intentions of the target group of customers (Mirabi et al., 2015).

Purchasing intentions can be important in many different areas and most importantly, understanding the importance of these in making better deliveries in managing the outcomes can be identified as important and needed (Soon & Wallace, 2017). Marketing is one of the most important identifications and further, it is coming as very important and needed for the best deliveries in the successful identification (Sheng, et al., 2019). There should be a return of the investments in the marketing actions, and this is causing the return for the marketing actions with increased intentions in the purchasing (Zhuang, et al., 2021). As per the literature, intentions are important for the organizational sales growth and to make the higher-level profits in the companies. Further, marketing actions can be designed in a manner to reach the customer in effective level, and this is making better deliveries in the successful outcome management as well (Zhang, et al., 2018).

Before the promotion, there is no intention or the idea of the products among the consumer minds and this is very important consideration for the better delivery identifications. Some of

the purchasing intention data can be the inputs in search engine optimization and even in the search engine marketing (Sheng, et al., 2019; Rahim, et al., 2016). All these actions are highly important and needed for the better marketing management. Some of the other areas that use the intent data are the customer relationship management that counts as important, and this is coming to the better understanding by the necessary levels (Xu, et al., 2018). Another important factor is intent data are used as the digital footprint to map the paths on the customer needs which is a trigger in the future developments. Along with these identifications, the purchasing intention can be recorded as highly important in the organizations specially in the marketing management applications.

2.7.2 Eco Friendly Aspects of Marketing

There are three factors that need the consideration, and these are provide as follows.

2.7.2.1 Impact of Environmental Awareness on Purchasing Intention

This is the understanding on the environment and the hazards happened in the environment due to the usage of the automobile. Environmental awareness is a needed factor as it manages the outcomes in effective level (Okada, et al., 2019). Another most important factor is understanding on the issues in the harmful level for the environment that comes as very important and further, it is coming as important and needed to manage the awareness level of the issues by the automobiles to manage the necessary deliveries in most effective level (Xu, et al., 2018). It is a must to have the better awareness on the environmental factors as it manages the necessary deliveries in a clear manner.

Environmental awareness is considering as one of the most important and needed application as it manages the huge applications related to the identifications in different purchasing applications. A study has been done by conducting an online survey in Japan from the non-Electrical Vehicle (EV) users and EV users (Okada, et al., 2019). This is mainly concerning about the environmental awareness as the EV are making better awareness and the acceptance in environmental applications while the non-EV are not much concerning on the environmental aspects. EV purchasing and the post satisfaction of the EV users are different from one another and it is highly showing that environmental awareness is playing an important role in the

purchasing applications and it is a must to consider better development in managing these identifications as it manages the different outcomes as per the study (Okada, et al., 2019).

Another important identification can be done with the research application explaining the intentions of purchasing the green furniture that is needed in explaining better developing applications. 460 respondents have been selected in the data collection and these respondents were selected from China (Xu, et al., 2020). There are empirical evidences showing that the environmental awareness is highly impacting on the willingness to pay, subjective norm, attitude and perceived behavioural control. The study has been used the theory of planned behaviour and the statistical analysis has undertaken in the results generation. Health consciousness is another factor that has been found as the higher impact on purchasing green variables which is counted as very important. Along with these identifications, it has been recorded that the environmental awareness is impacting on the green furniture purchasing and it is highly needed to understand the customer on the reasons of the purchasing as well (Xu, et al., 2020).

Another research has been done focusing the belt and road countries and the study is mainly focusing on the factors impacting on the purchasing intentions and mainly green factors have been considered in a clear level. 227 valid responses have been taken into consideration and this is very important consideration, which is coming as critical and further, it is counted as important and needed to understand the different factors that is needed in consideration as well (Chen, et al., 2018). The study has pointed out several identifications and these are environmental awareness, social attitude, perceived monetary value and the product attitude and these variables are highly impacted on the development applications and purchasing intentions which are necessary and important in managing better development identifications. Further, it has been recorded that the understanding and knowing the impact of environmental analysis is very important and needed as it manages the outcomes in most effective manner (Chen, et al., 2018).

Further, another study has showed the impacts of the green supply chain management and green marketing applications on the green purchasing intentions in SME in Indonesia. This is a primary research application, and the data collection has been done from the environmental oriented SMEs and further, statistical analysis has been done in the answers and the outcome generation (Sugandini, et al., 2020). The study is showing that there is a scarcity of the evidence and the practices that is needed in the considerations, and it is identified that the green practices

are highly impacting on the purchasing intentions, and it is counted as important to manage the actions in making better deliveries in the organizational identifications. It is showing that the greens supply chain is impacting in a higher level in the purchasing intention and in the similar times, green marketing is also increasing the aspects in most effective manner (Sugandini, et al., 2020).

Likewise, there are studies that are needed to understand and that are needed to identified in a clear manner where these are highly showing the environmental awareness impacting on the purchasing intentions in different products and the services in an effective manner (Asif, et al., 2018; Suki, 2016; Indriani, et al., 2019; Sreen, et al., 2018; Jung & Seock, 2016; Hsu, et al., 2017; Tan, et al., 2017).

2.7.2.2 Impact of Green Perceived Value on Purchasing Intention

This is the net benefit on the products and the services that the consumer is received verses the benefit that the consumer is expecting as per the desires on the environmental concerns and the protection applications (Lam, et al., 2016). This is coming as important in the organizations as it increases the desire in purchasing and this is needed to be provided by the organizations to manage the necessary outcomes in most effective levels (Lin, et al., 2017). The comparison of the products is been undertaking by the customer once purchasing and the better and higher value products that provides the higher benefits to the customer is purchased by the customer in most of the cases (Wang & Hazen, 2016). This is a common behaviour by the customers who are in line with the expectations of the green perceived value.

This is becoming as very important and needed factor to understand the impact of the green perceived value impact on the green purchasing actions. It is counted as very important and needed to consider the outcomes in most effective manner and it is counted that the green trust is another important identification which is needed to be recorded as important (Lam, et al., 2016). The study is investigating the mediation of the green perceived value and green trust on the green purchasing applications which is counted as very important and needed. The study has showed that the need of organizational to increase the resources applications in increasing the use of green aspects which is counted as one of the needed identifications in managing better deliveries. Green trust and the satisfaction are found to have strong mediation impacts

on the green value and the purchasing intention which is needed consideration (Lam, et al., 2016).

Another study has been undertaken regarding the green benefits, green transparency on green perceived values and green consumption. The study is showing that mediation role in the green perceived value among the relationships of green benefits, green transparency and brand loyalty (Lin, et al., 2017). It is counted that this is very important consideration, and the study has been undertaken in the China Mainland. It is counted that the primary data has been used in the research and the data were collected from 826 respondents in China which the statistical analysis is been undertaken in testing the necessary hypotheses in the study. It is showing that organizations are needed to have diversified green management applications and it is counted that usage of these applications make better purchasing options for the customers (Lin, et al., 2017).

Lack of consumer acceptance in the products can be seen and it is necessary to have better delivery identifications as it manages the outcomes in most effective level in managing the purchases. Along with this identification, this study is referring to the investigation of the remanufactured products purchasing intention of the customer as per the cost, quality and green attributes which is counted as very important and needed. This is researching the purchasing intention of the products with receptive to the China (Wang & Hazen, 2016). The analysis is been done with the structural equation modelling and it is further showing that perceived value is positively impacted on the purchasing intention of the remanufactured products which are green and perceived risk is negatively impacted on the purchasing intention which is counted as one of the most important identifications. Along with this identification, it is recorded that management policies are needed to be developed in most effective level in order to understand these aspects in a clear level and this is further resulting the proper developing identifications in most effective manner (Wang & Hazen, 2016).

Another study has been carried out to investigate the influence of environmental, collectivism, perceived consumer effectiveness of green purchase behaviour and it revealed that consumer environmental affect attitude does not necessarily result in green product purchase (Marvi et al,2020). Their results showed that environmental involvement, information utility, green advertising, and green trust have a positive impact on the customer attitude towards green products which results in green purchase intention. Also, they have found that media positively

impacted to green purchase intention among green product consumers. Therefore, with these identifications, companies should evaluate the possible future purchase intention of green purchase strategy, green purchase positioning with the help of social media. Consequently, managers should adjust their marketing strategy to influence the purchase behaviour (Marvi et al., 2020).

Another research has been undertaken with respect to the green energy and it is showing that the green energy is a needed factor for the better developing identifications where it manages the successful deliveries in a clear level. Application in green energy is not done solely with the government regulations but it needs the willingness in using the green energy as well (Sangroya & Nayak, 2017). This willingness has been enhanced by the consumers' perceived value towards the usage of green energy. Multidimensional green perceived value scale developing has been done in order to investigate the current level of the consumer perception on usage of the green energy. It is very important and recorded that the green perceived value is one of the most important identifications and need which is coming as very important and needed in making the better developing applications in managing the perceptions and the purchasing intentions (Sangroya & Nayak, 2017).

Likewise, there are many studies focusing on this application and showing that the green perceived value is making the necessary illustrations in managing better deliveries and aspects in managing the successful identifications (Wu, et al., 2015; Ghazali, et al., 2017; Jamal & Sharifuddin, 2015; Trang, et al., 2019; Chaudhary & Bisai, 2018; Degirmenci & Breitner, 2017).

2.7.2.3 Impact of Green Trust on Purchasing Intention

This is the willingness in depending on a certain product or a service that is needed in understanding the identifications as per the beliefs and the expectations resulting in the product or the service which is coming as critical from its credibility and the ability in environmental performances (Amin & Tarun, 2020). This is the trusting of the products and the services as per the provided identifications on the environmentally friendly performance management that comes as very important and needed in understanding the outcomes which comes as very important and needed (Al-Quran, et al., 2020). Green trust is a positive point where the customers who are having the green trust results the needed outcomes in a clear level which is

resulting the positive feedbacks and the positive outcomes in trusting the products (Cheung, et al., 2015). Once the organizations are failing to provide the environmentally friendly products or the services or the organization is failing to perform as per the trusted level by the customer, distrust can be resulted that is negatively impacting on the performance level of the organization.

Green trust is a counting variable that is mentioning in many of the applications and it is counted as very important to have the clear understanding on the measures of the green trust as it manages the outcomes in most effective manner. Along with this application, mediating role of the green trust among the relationship of the consumption values and the green purchasing intention has been created in most effective manner (Amin & Tarun, 2020). Cross sectional research design has been used in this research and further, statistical methods were used in the investigation. It is clearer in the research that emotional values are playing as important in the green purchasing intentions and further it is clear that the green trust has the most significant impact on the green purchasing applications which is counted as very important and needed in making better decisions on the green purchasing actions. Green consumption business strategies are needed to be clearly planned and recorded in effective manner and this is counted as very important and needed to manage the impacts in most effective level (Amin & Tarun, 2020).

Understanding the determinants of the green purchasing intention is very important and needed as it counts in better developments and the applications in different industries. Here, several identifications were taken into the consideration and the investigation where the environmental attitude, green satisfaction, green trust and the green perceived quality have been taken into consideration on the investigation on understanding the necessary identifications on making better impacts on the purchasing intention of the products and the services (Al-Quran, et al., 2020). Along with this identification, FMCG industry has been selected and the statistical methods were used in the investigation as well. It has been identified that the selected variables are having the positive significant impact on the green purchasing intention which is counted as very important. Further, it is necessary in the delivery actions in managing the successful identifications on making the better deliveries that counts as important and further, it is making better development applications on managing green trust on the success level as well in managing the better outcomes for the customers to have the green purchasing intentions (Al-Quran, et al., 2020).

Drivers of the green product adoption is been considered and it is necessary identification in managing the better deliveries and further, it is counted as very important and needed to manage the better identification on the green product adoption for the better delivery actions as well (Cheung, et al., 2015). The study has collected the primary data and 188 respondents were selected as the sample here and it is further recorded that the green perceived value and the perceived quality are having the direct and significant impacts on the green purchasing intention of the products while the green trust is showing a mediation among these relationships (Cheung, et al., 2015). In the similar time, the green trust is showing the relationship with the green purchasing intention as well which is counted as important. Thus, the drivers of the green product adoption have bene identified in a clear manner and this is showing that the green trust is playing an important role in managing better outcomes in most effective manner (Cheung, et al., 2015).

There are many such studies showing the green trust as a determinant and the understanding of these relationships is coming as important and needed in deciding he factors that are impacted on the purchasing intentions of the products. There are literature showing similar results (Doszhanov & Ahmad, 2015; Nam, et al., 2017; Chen, et al., 2015; Wei, et al., 2017; Agmeka, et al., 2019).

2.7.3 Brand and Brand Image

2.7.3.1 Brand

As identified by marketing Association,1975, Brand could be defined as a name, sign, symbol or design or collection of them. Brand reduces the risk and complexity involved in the purchasing decision. It is vital to every industry from steel to software due to the overwhelming number of suppliers. (Kotler and Pfoertsch 2007). Due to the functional capabilities of the brands people started to identify them differently with distinctive names (De Chernatony, 1997). Brands can add or subtract the perceived value of a product. Consumers expect to pay lower prices for unbranded products or for those with low brand equities, whereas they pay premiums for their treasured or socially valued brands (Kotler, P. and Gertner, D., 2002). Brand also recognises as a key asset of a business (Wood 2008). Auto brands have constituted an important part of the branded society if cars have existed – the car industry was one of the first

to use branding on a broad basis, something that underlines its strong position in 20th century societal history. Unlikely in any other sectors, the brand is at the heart of success in the car industry. For car purchasers' brand is a critical factor consciously or unconsciously car buyers are attracted to.

Marketers have established a quality brand essentially having opinions not only from the car buyers, but also a complex set of opinions and ideas from other stakeholders too. Hence, auto makers have tried their best to establish attractive and profitable auto brands (Adrian, 2015). He analysed that car makers spent enormous amounts on establishing and strengthening their auto brands. It's a collaboration of corporate identity, product design, advertising, competency of salesperson etc. He also pointed out that even car makers investing a lot of money to have a perceived car brand is going to be worth it in future.

2.7.3.2 Brand Image Empirical Evidence

There are several empirical evidence that can be recorded as important in understanding on different aspects and this is coming as very important and needed to manage these understanding on the literature applications in most effective and clear manner.

This is simply the perception of the brand that is there in the minds of the customer. Understanding this perception is very important as it manages the necessary outcomes in a most effective and needed manner. this is the ideas, beliefs, and the impressions that the customer is having regarding any product or the service with the brand name (Hien, et al., 2020). There can be different perceptions of the customer and the marketers are needed to have higher level of brand image among the customers as it manages the outcomes in most effective and important level which is coming as very important and needed (Lee & Lee, 2018). In other words, brand image offers description of consumer's thoughts and feeling about a brand (Roy & Jee, 2007). Brand image involves consumer's knowledge and beliefs about product-related and non-product related attributes of the brand (Keller 2001). A favourable brand image have had a positive influence on consumer behaviour about a brand such as increasing brand loyalty, managing a price premium, and generating positive word-of-mouth (Martenson, 2007). It has been found that brand image influences the intellectual aspects of consumer's attitudes towards the new products marked with its sign. It was found that the customers with strongly fixed brand image have been much more resistance to promotional activities of the competitors' brands (Park, et al., 2010). Moreover, he recommended that as a practice of marketing

management, car producers must do intensive work into shaping of brand image and identity as it has contributed to the brand loyalty among customers. Along with these identifications, it is necessary to understand the outcomes of the brand image of the products and the customer perception towards this brand image to manage the outcomes in most effective level (Tariq, et al., 2017). Brand image comes as very important and needed in considering these activities where the organizations are needed to strive to maintain a proper brand image that is coming as important and needed and it is a highly needed application as well.

2.7.3.3 Mediation of Brand Image

Brand image is playing an important role in the organizational contexts. It is counted as very important and needed in understanding the necessary outcomes and further it is coming as very important and needed to manage the outcomes with most important and successful manner. Along with this identification, a study has been done and investigated that brand image (Hien, et al., 2020) and brand evaluation are playing an important role and it is recorded that this mediation is between the country-of-origin image and the purchasing intention of the customers. This study has been done 283 customers about the household appliances and further it has found that the organizational development can be achieved with higher level of purchasing intention that comes as a very important identification. Along with this factor, brand image comes as a very important application and this is recorded as very important and needed in managing better deliveries (Hien, et al., 2020).

Another research has been done in investigating the impact of the electronic word of mouth and brand awareness impact on the purchasing intention and the impact of brand image of a mediating role in these connections (Tariq, et al., 2017). This is done with respect to the 300 customers in mobile users. It is considered that the electronic word of mouth is a strong predictor of the purchasing intention. Along with this identification, it has been recorded that the brand image is mediating these relationships in a successful manner which is necessary in developing better developments in the organizational management and action development. With the outcomes of the research, marketers can implement better strategic applications in making the successful deliveries in the most effective manner (Tariq, et al., 2017).

Brand image is acting as a strong application which is making the needed outcomes, and this has recorded as very important and needed in making better delivery identifications on managing the marketing strategic outcomes in most effective level (Lee & Lee, 2018). It has been investigated the impact of the CSR activities on the purchasing intention of the products and the mediating role of the brand image has been taken as important identification that makes the most important deliveries. 113 respondents were selected in the study and it has been recorded that the CSR actions and the reciprocity perception of these CSR actions is highly and directly impacting on the purchasing intention and it is counted as very important to manage the proper brand image in making the successful delivery actions in strategy development (Lee & Lee, 2018).

A study has conducted using customers who have already used the green products in country Pakistan. Green packaging has increased the customer perception about the green products and has affected to increase purchase intention. It has found that green brand image successfully allows firms to increase green purchases due to the green products strategy which premium and pricing as consumers pay more for the environmentally friendly goods than the environmentally inferior product. This has also revealed that customer belief towards the environment considerably mediate the connection between green labeling and purchase intention. It has recommended that firms should consider the mediating role of the brand image on purchase intention when developing environmentally friendly strategies their consequences they have on producing value in business contexts (Majeed et al., 2022).

Another important identification can be recorded as the brand image and brand trust are acting as the mediators in a relationship which the green brand knowledge, attitude, environment knowledge is acting as the predictors of the purchasing intention in the organizations. This is very important consideration where 300 respondents from Pakistan have been selected in the research activity. Further, it has been recorded that the analysis is been done in statistical methods to investigate the outcomes in most effective level (Tan, et al., 2022). It has shown the positive and significant relationships among the green brand knowledge, attitude and the environmental knowledge and purchasing intention. Further, it has investigated that the mediating role is also showing the significant relationships. This is very important identification in making the decisions on the applications and further it is showing that green marketing is one of the applications that can be done in making the better deliveries in managing the outcomes for the better delivery actions in the organizational contexts. It further

explains the multidimensional green marketing approaches in developing better purchasing intention and this is making the huge impact on the organizational strategic direction development (Tan, et al., 2022).

Likewise, there are different studies that have been done in past and explaining the outcomes in most effective manner in explaining the mediating role of the brand image in managing the outcomes can be recorded here with the best interests (Shabbir, et al., 2017; Porral & Lang, 2015; Indriani, et al., 2019; Nyadzayo & Khajehzadeh, 2016; Chen, et al., 2020).

Along with these above findings, the conceptual framework has been developed in a clear manner as shown as follows.

Figure 0-4: Conceptual Framework

2.8 Research Gap

Marketing management is a prevailing concept in many of the industries and this is highly important in understanding the outcomes and the other needed applications in a clear level which is coming as very important and needed in the investigation. Still, green marketing or the eco-friendly marketing concepts are not been used in the discussion in deep manner in many of the literature. It is very important consideration to understand the outcomes and it is further discussed in a clear manner to manage the necessary deliveries in most effective manner in managing discussions on the green marketing actions and green management actions in the organizations which shows the lack in discussion. Thus, the current research has been done in order to fill this research gap. Automobile industry is another important industry where there are less studies in the green marketing concept. There are studies in the purchasing intention applications in cars and the automobiles where green marketing concept impact in purchasing cars is not in a clear and deep level. This is resulting another research gap that is needed to be discussed. Sri Lankan automobile industry is in the lack in studies and there is no huge focus in the recent studies on the automobile industry making a knowledge gap in the literature. Automobile industry is not that much developed and prevailing industry in the Sri Lanka context, and this can be the main reason for this application which is a need in investigation as well. Accordingly, there is a gap prevailing in the existing literature and there is a gap in the knowledge shares in the literature as well. Along with these identifications, it is counted as very important and needed to consider these identifications and actions to manage the filling of the research gaps in most effective manner. Branding comes as one of the most important identifications and there are different types of branding activities that can be taken into consideration. Likewise, there are many aspects that is needed to be filled and the present study is responsible on filling these gaps in most effective manner in a clear level. Still, there are no branding application has been used as the mediation on the eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention relationship which is prevailing as a gap in the prevailing literature.

2.9 Chapter Summary

To sum up, we could say that aiming the available information about green marketing strategy and car industry this chapter has been built. Related articles have been referred to provide good understanding and analysing existing literature to cover the topics green marketing, environmental awareness, perceived value, green trust, brand image and purchase intention. Further, interrelationships between variables used in the research have been explained accordance with research context. Various research papers have been discussed to provide some knowledge about variables to different stakeholders about eco-friendliness and green marketing. Through discussing the relationships, the chapter has recognized the reliability of aspects which have been discussed.

CHAPTER 3: SEPARATE CHAPTER IN THE CONTEXT OF SRI LANKA

This chapter briefly explains the present car market situation and the issues concerning in Sri Lankan car market and the environment. It also discusses challenges along with opportunities, consumers, and eco-friendliness in respect of green car promotion in the country.

3.1 Automobile Industry in Sri Lanka

Automobile industry recognized as one of the growing industries that can be recorded as important and needed in making better arrangements in considering the vehicle parts and the vehicles applications (Rathnayaka, 2021). To understand the definitions in the automobile industry, the explanation has been provided in a clear level by the scholars. The explanation has been provided in the automobile industry as the activities that are included in the manufacturing of the vehicles, bodies, components, and the engines (Ranasinghe & Alwis, 2021). These vehicles are including the passenger cars and the other light trucks such as the van, pickup trucks, and Sports Utility Vehicles (SUV). In the present study, automobile industry with the car manufacturers and the dealers are taken into consideration in Sri Lanka, manufacturing has not been undertaking within the country at large but the dealers are mainly comprised in the automobile industry in Sri Lanka (Silva & Fernando, 2020).

Many authors always start with the Henry ford and the model T as introduction to their literature (Holweg 2008). It is often said to be the beginning of the automobile industry that's the roots of present industry can be found there, but the real foundation of today's motor vehicle can be found there. Researchers have defined two eras prior to the initiation of the assembly line for the Ford Model T as establishment era 1904-1924 (Camp & Abel 2011). First, they have described the initiation era (pre-1888), when Austrain Siegfried Marcus designed the first automobile in 1870 which ran on internal liquid fuel. This car was the basis for the world's first automobile powered by a gasoline-driven engine with internal combustion, designed by Karl Benz in 1885 (Camp & Abel 2011). Benz was seen as the inventor of the automobile powered by an internal -combustion engine (Eckerman 2001, 31-31). In this era, Henry ford introduced the assembly line which marks the beginning of the mass production of motorized vehicles. In the eras to come, the 'pre-war' (1930-1948), 'post war' (1949-1970) and the 'modern era' (1970-present) the car industry has further emerged globally. All brands have kept introducing new features into the market. American producers have focused on technology

and low unit cost, European producers have focused on quality and durability while Toyota (Japan) become competitive by their innovative Just-In-Time and quality management system or the so-called Toyota production system (Abel et al., 2011,).

In Sri Lanka, car market has started in 1900 and this has a longer history with better applications. The first car was entered in Sri Lanka in 1902 and first petrol car was imported to the country in 1905 (Jayalath & Wedasinghe, 2020). At that time, the roads were not in the needed standards to drive the cars and specially there were no roads suitable in riding in village areas (Imran, et al., 2018; Rathnayaka, 2021). Still, the development of the roads also has occurred in 1940s and the development of the better delivery of the rural areas also have developed in this time. This application of the motoring was not only impacted on the easiness on the transportation but also it has impacted on the higher level on the economic growth and the changes in the social exchanging applications as well (Silva & Fernando, 2020).

Automobile sector in Sri Lanka is mainly consisting with the motor vehicles retail sector and after sales service sector. There is no manufacturing in the automobile in the country and this retailing is undertaking in a higher level (Wimalarathna, et al., 2020). The developed automobile process is a gap in the Sri Lankan context as it is managing the successful entry in other countries and the facility lacking and the motivation and the influence lacking in this sector can be seen in a very higher level (Rathnayaka, 2021). Thus, mainly, importing automobiles from the foreign countries and assembling automobiles were the main part and the action that is been undertaking in the automobile industry in the Sri Lankan context. However, there are two companies identified which manufacturing cars within the country and owned by Sri Lanka namely Vega Innovations totally produce electric cars and Micro cars which is a subsidiary of Micro holdings. Since 1902, this industry in the country is facing many more challenges and overcoming these challenges are becoming as very important and needed factor (Jayalath & Wedasinghe, 2020). Pandemic was a great threat for the industry and in the similar manner, many policy changes were occurred in the automobile industry and understanding these policies and adjusting for them is becoming a huge problem (Subhani, et al., 2022). Tax on the imported stuff is one of the main challenges and another policy is there that the 30 % of the automobile assembling is needed to be using the Sri Lankan manufactured parts. Lack in the space in the country and the facilities are also coming as a concerning factor in the automobile industry which is coming as very important and needed. Similarly due to the

prevailing environment pollution due to the increased usage of vehicles in the country, car market also has faced for the different issues (Jayalath & Wedasinghe, 2020).

Automobile industry considered as one of the main contributors to the government revenue through import taxes 4.5 billion LKR in 2020. Among the total vehicle population in the country, third most popular vehicle type is motor cars after the highest of motor bicycles and three wheelers. Considering the numerical values vehicle registrations, the registration of motor cars, three wheelers, and motor bicycles have made significant contribution to the increasing number of vehicle population in Sri Lanka (Department of Motor Traffic, 2020) refer Annexure: 02. Early 2020, with the government restrictions on import of automobiles including motor cars which new car registrations has fallen drastically. It was 21,021 in the year 2020 compared to 80,776 in 2018 and 38,232 in 2019 which was affected by covid 19 pandemic (Road and motor vehicle department, 2022).

In fact, this has negatively affected to the automobile industry including car market in Sri Lanka. Among the different contributing factors of Sri Lanka's poor air quality, the notable increase in private car ownership has been commonly regarded as a major cause by government and media. Air emissions check carried out with the objective of preventing air pollution and controlling the air emission from vehicles which contribute towards air pollution. Standards have declared and in forced with effect from 2016 and press notices have been published and community awareness programmers have been conducted to protect the environment pollution as governments initiatives to mitigate the environmental pollution.

During the first eight months of 2018, imports of motor vehicles rose significantly, due to the importation of personal vehicles, particularly vehicles with small engine capacity, and hybrid and electric vehicles. This situation has completely changed with the restrictions imposed after 2018. Due to the import suspension, the motor car trade has been crippled and has lost over 10,000 jobs following two years of the import restriction. Further, over 1,500 dealers, which were SME's based island-wide, have closed which has a direct impact on the rural economy. Due to the ongoing economic crisis the increase in inflation to over 64% has also adversely affected to the motor car industry which employees have left the industry as well as the country to find new employments (Ceylon Motor Traders Association, 2022). But even negative impact occurred economically it has positively impacted from the environmental perspective due to less mobility of the personal vehicles in the country. In 2006, Asia accounted for 19% of global

transport CO₂ emissions. By 2030 environmentalists have predicted that share would rise to 31%. Asian Development Bank (ADB) has taken initiatives to reduce energy consumption and promote the shift to zero emission transport systems by supporting transport investments and it has identified Sri Lankan automobile industry as one of major contributors to the CO₂ emission. This is highly applicable in the case of promoting eco-friendly cars and country is needed to increase eco-friendly vehicles to protection of environment and marketers should persuade the potential customers to purchase green cars. In this concern, the green narratives promoted by Sri Lanka's auto advertisements has continued to be a critical part in the public debates on country's deteriorating environmental harm.

The decline in the automotive sales have started during the easter Sunday terrorist attack on the country which was followed by a ban on imports to save the much-needed foreign exchange. Further imports have slowed down due to the government revised and increased the excise duty for automotive vehicles in the country with the negative contribution to the car market. Ban was imposed at a time where public transport was not convenient and there was a demand for other vehicles such as two wheelers. Companies have been selling vehicles from their inventory, but they do not have any inventory to sell after 2020. Many small dealerships have closed shop during this period as they did not have enough inventory to stay in business and this has also led to massive unemployment. After that country have faced for the covid 19 which was spread all over the world desperately.

3.2 Impact of Covid-19 on the car industry in Sri Lanka

Car industry in Sri Lanka could be identified as one of the industries which contributes greatly to economic growth, regional and rural development, employment generation, and eradicating poverty (Manzoor, 2021). Due to the Covid-19 pandemic car industry in Sri Lanka also got adversely affected like many other industries in the world. With the suspension of car manufacturing in Europe, deserted tourist destinations, stopped travels between nations etc have adversely affected to the world economy and for the Sri Lankan car market (James and Kengatharan, 2020). Most of the companies have started to close as the economic crisis increased in the country. This pandemic situation has been really worrying not just for one industry

in the country but also for the entire national economy since it affected to all businesses of Sri Lanka.

Covid-19 pandemic has massively changed human behaviour and it has brought positive results for the environment. Due to the serious lockdown and travel restriction industrial manufacturing and supply chain have been dramatically reduced around the world and in Sri Lanka most of the industries got negatively affected. Transport (emission from motor vehicles), industry (power generation) and domestic uses has been identified as the main sources of air pollution in Sri Lanka. Public transport within these cities was limited during the lockdown period to prevent the spread of the virus. Similarly with the reduction of burning fossil fuel carbon emission to the environment has been reduced drastically. Like many other countries, in Sri Lanka urban cities mostly polluted with the carbon emission from the vehicles and it was 60% and balance due to other activities (Senarathna et al., 2021). During the year 2020, as a result of the lockdown most human activities affected, and fewer motor vehicles were on the roads. Considerable reduction of air pollution has been identified due to the restriction on transport and reduction in industrial activities. Even it was negatively affected to car industry and other industries this has caused to reduction in air pollution and have had short-term health benefits such as reduced hospital admissions for respiratory problems, cardiovascular illness, asthma, and premature death. Minimizing vehicles and industrial pollution will improve air quality in urban areas and help sustain better public health.

With the adverse economic condition affected to the country after Covid-19, it has faced for an economic crisis which extended up to the recent years. Due to the ongoing economic crisis and the car industry deterioration occurred recent years has been the major reason to carry out this research. Mercedes, Audi, Toyota, Honda, Suzuki, Mitsubishi, Nissan, Volkswagen, Tesla are the major car brands available in Sri Lanka. Those have also met some hardships from the economic downturn. Even the customers have looked for purchase hassle free those brands some of them have closed. When brands are strong then they become worthwhile for the customers and purchase them while gives companies chances to earn high market share, profits, increased share values and goodwill. Automobile sector in Sri Lanka is growing and one of the key drivers of economy growth. But we do not have relevant literature present which can tell us about perception of purchase intention of cars with the mediation effects of brands image and from the environment friendly marketing perspective.

Understanding of this research will help marketing and brand professionals in allocation of appropriate resources for executing their marketing plans as well as for the car production & selling companies so to focus on variables such as brand image, green marketing with green trust and perceived quality to the customers. Automotive market in Sri Lanka is quite volatile which is normal phenomenon for any automotive market in the world. Different types of brands have been operating in the Sri Lankan market such as Toyota, Honda, Suzuki, Mitsubishi, Nissan, Volkswagen, Ford, BMW, Mercedes, Tesla etc. These branded cars sell by companies namely Toyota Lanka (Pvt) Ltd, Prestige Automobile (Pvt) Ltd, Micro cars (Pvt) Ltd, and Nissan Sri Lanka, Dima (Pvt) Ltd etc. Car market consists with several distributors and few manufacturer's outlets within the country. As the department of motor traffic, 2020 stated that Majority of automobiles imported from Japan, India, Germany, France while India and Japan continued to be the largest supplier in terms of volume and value respectively. In Sri Lanka, few numbers of luxury cars can be found while non luxury cars are the most popular in the market. Consumers who have ability to spend more on their cars purchase luxury cars not only for the technical attributes of the car, but also for non-technical attributes such as perceived image, brand name, value to show off their status (DK and Wanninayake, 2015). To increase the sale of luxury and non-luxury cars, companies marketing division has a huge responsibility towards attracting customers. As a result, companies change into green marketing is essential as to find out environmental issues together with all parties such as consumers, firms, and organizations (Polonsky, 2011). In line with those practices most of the companies need to broaden their activities, creating alternative ways of delivering value and costs, changing behaviour of the corporations to be successful in the business of selling cars while thinking about human interactions and the environment.

When consumers make purchase decisions, they have to face for more alternatives due to the information exchange and the criteria's which they value during purchase. Additionally, there are other factors, such as demographic factors which affect to purchase car in any market. Price features and safety, family and friends influence, other transport mode effect such as car sharing, government infrastructure facilities, second-hand cars etc could be identified as several other deciding factors of car purchase decision. But in this research, we are not focusing on those factors and mainly consider eco-friendliness, green marketing effects and brand image for the purchase intention of automobile in Sri Lanka. Even these have researched based on the other countries, in Sri Lankan car market we could see very limited research have conducted in this area. Consequently, there is a necessity to investigate Sri Lankan car industry. The

researchers have covered different parts of the globe inclusive of United States (US), Spain, Turkey, India, China, Austria, Korea, and United Kingdom (UK) among many other countries, but it is hard to find a study which has been conducted for product category of cars in country Sri Lanka of SA region recently.

CHAPTER 4: METHODOLOGY

4.1 Chapter Introduction

The chapter is mainly explaining about the methodology that is used in the research to understand the process of the study. Main purpose of developing academic research is to have an understanding a chosen research context is so that prepared research questions can be addressed as per the requirement of the research. Several stages are needed to be identified to conduct successful research. Specifically, research methods help for the researcher to find a solution to any recognized problem (Stahl and King, 2020). An explanation of the research design with the research onion framework is explained here. Further, hypotheses development, population and sample explanation, data collection methods, and the data collection instrument explanation are also well delivered in this chapter. Additionally, operationalization and the data analysis method are also well explained in this chapter.

4.2 Research Design

The research design has been explaining with the incorporation of the research onion method. There are several stages in research onion that is needed to be recorded. The research onion is provided in the following figure (Saunders et al.,2007)

Figure 0-1: Research onion

Source: (Saunders et al.,2007)

Qualitative research approach Design diagram Annexure:03 illustrates qualitative design which consists of several steps.

4.3 Research Philosophy

Normally research philosophy deals with the source, nature, and development of knowledge. In simpler terms, it is known as the system of the researcher's thought come out which new and reliable knowledge regarding the selected research objectives can be obtained. Research philosophy sits as the core of the research methodology and as provision of necessary directions for the researcher. As a result, it is critical to identify the research philosophy at the beginning of the research process. To check the mediation effect of branding between eco-friendly marketing in Sri Lankan car buyers, researcher allowed to analyse people's perspectives and then analysing the data collected in both qualitatively and quantitatively. There are several research philosophies namely positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism and realism. Pragmatism research philosophy is applicable in the case of mixed methods of research or data triangulation where collected data is analysed both theoretically and numerically. As the Study is considered about both qualitative and quantitative methods, this research philosophy is matching with the research. The selected research philosophy here is the pragmatism research philosophy (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). This means that this philosophy accepts only data which has been supported by actions. This philosophy has a strong belief that there is no point of view as far as comprehending all associated aspects associated with the research context. Hence, multiple realities need to be accepted. The main objective of this research is to recognize Mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on Car purchasing Intention Sri Lanka. Pragmatism research found to be most suitable as the researcher considered various aspects and whole study that has been consisted of depend upon factual data collection from a real-time scenario to reach this aim. This is specific because this research permitted the researcher to analyse people's perceptions and then analysing the collected raw data both qualitatively and quantitatively. This philosophy has enforced great importance on peoples' perceptions and has ultimately ignored behavioural aspects which could have misled this research.

4.4 Research Approach

Research approach has been explained as the process of plan which helps researcher to identification of successful methods, connected with data collection, analysis, and interpretation as well as make wider assumptions. Research approach should always selected depend up on the nature of the research objectives and problems. There are three types as the deductive, inductive research approach and abductive research approach. Deductive research approach makes the explanation on the past literature and the inductive research approach makes the explanation on the newly designed theories (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). For successful usage of a deductive reasoning approach, the researcher needs to develop a few hypotheses which can be evaluated effectively. Present research is mainly concluding with past literature and thus, deductive research approach is most matching. This has helped researcher to consider the data collected and match with the existing theories and principles with an impartial approach. Current study focusing on recognizing mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on Car purchasing Intention Sri Lanka and therefore, the research expect to analyze whether pre-existing theories were useful to deliver meaningful results expected. Critical factors are being identified to have positive outcome of the research. Hence for the successful completion of this research, deductive research approach has been used.

4.5 Research Method

There are three types as qualitative, quantitative, and mixed method. Usage of the numerical measures and the numerical applications mainly undertaken in quantitative method research (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). Present research is one of the mixed research projects as it is using both numerical and statistical methods in the investigation and interviews to get details for the qualitative research part.

4.6 Research Strategies

Overall planning of the carrying out the research could be identified as the research strategy. There are several research strategies such as survey, questionnaires, case study, experimental research, ethnographic and observations (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). Present research is undertaking with the survey and questionnaire method, and this is undertaken with statistical data collection and the interview feedback from the people. Questionnaires included in respect for the eco-friendliness, marketing, green trust, purchase intention. The participants were contacted through phone, emails, video calls to collect the primary data for the qualitative research section while online survey used for the quantitative data collection. Interviews were carried out for 45-60 minutes. Recoded interview data used for the transcript and for coding to analyse through Thematic analysis. Researcher could explore the personal feelings, beliefs of the participants to achieve research position. This also helped to in depth understand of the personal views and perceptions. Statistics were used to analyse the quantitative data percentage, graphs, and charts. Responses gathered from online survey have analysed by using statistical analysis such as mean, median and mode. To reach a solid research outcome these were helped. To find out the information which required for the literature review, relevant and reliable sources used. To collect that information wide range of journal articles used. Using Google Scholar, Science Direct, Emerald Insights, journal articles selected.

4.7 Quantitative Research Method

4.7.1 Hypothesis Development

There are several hypotheses that have been developed are as follows for the quantitative research part.

H1: Environmental awareness in marketing is having significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka

H2: Green perceived value in marketing is having significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka

H3: Green trust in marketing is having significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka

H4: Brand image is mediating the relationship between eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka

4.7.2 Population and Sample

The population is the total targeted group of any research. The population is targeted to get the needed data. This is a very significant portion and here, all the citizens in the country who have an interest in eco-friendly cars can be the population. The population cannot be measured exactly. Reaching the population in data collection is not an easy task and thus, the researcher has decided to select a sample. The sample is selected from the identified population and here, simple random sampling has been selected as the sample selection. Every person is having a similar probability of getting selected for the sample. As the population number is very higher, a sample of 384 (the highest number in the Morgan table) has been selected as the sample number. From all the districts of the country Sri Lanka who has interest in eco-friendly cars have been chosen as population in this study while majority were selected from the capital city Colombo. This was carried out through an online survey.

Data collection is the process of gathering and collecting relevant and suitable information required for assessing research outcomes, and in considering the chosen research context (Kumar, 2018). The data collection method can be of two types. One is secondary data collection, and the other is primary data collection. Along with these applications, primary data collection has been used in this section of the research which is quantitative research analysis. These data are used in statistical methods in analysing the necessary outcomes. For the quantitative part of the research is used respondents from the sample and a survey is conducted in collecting the needed data for the analysis.

Primary data are real-time data that have been collected concerning the respondents through sample surveys and interviews. Target participants were car owners and the dealers to have a proper judgement of the topic. Sri Lanka is a country with population of 21Mn (2020) and comprising area 65,610sq meters as the statistics have been taken from the Department of Census of Sri Lanka, 2020. Samples from the whole country were selected to carry out the qualitative questions about passenger car ownerships. It was hard to contact the participants face to face because they were in Sri Lanka and unable to contact easily due to the Covid-19 restrictions. The participants included 22 men and 08 women with an age range of 18-60. They were selected based on the provinces in the country to have a reasonable conclusion for the study by not being biased for a particular region. Colombo is the capital city of Sri Lanka, and it was selected higher number of participants from that province which city belonged.

Moreover, most of the car owners have reported in the Colombo than other cities in the country. This has helped researcher to come to a strong conclusion and therefore majority were selected from the capital city (Road and Motor Vehicle Department, 2020). Classification of the interviewees; distribution by sectors, companies, and geographic scope of activities are presented in Annexure: 04.

The capital city, Colombo is the main city which consists of most passenger car ownerships. It is considered as the main commercial city and the rest of the participants were from other main cities of each province in the country. Sri Lanka was chosen due to its convenience and accessibility for the research.

4.7.3 Data Collection Instrument

The systematic approach of the collecting and analysing data provide proper solutions for the research questions and achieve research objectives which is identified as data collection in the research. It helps to find out information to tests hypothesis and assumptions evaluation made throughout the research (Malhotra et al., 2017). Research data or information could be collected through reliable various sources and which we could categorized as primary and secondary data techniques. There are different instruments in the data collection. Primary data collection processes can be further classified as qualitative research and quantitative research methods (Moser and Korstjens, 2018). Here, primary data are collected with respect to the self-administrated questionnaire for the quantitative research part of the study. This questionnaire is consisting of five-point Likert scale questions and there are demographic variables that are used in the data collection. Respondents are expected to answer these questions as per their opinion. Unbiased answers are expected from the sample respondents to generate better outcomes using numerical values in the quantitative research part.

Qualitative data is the opposite side of the above quantitative data, and it includes viewpoints, emotions, feelings, perceptions etc. In this section of the research secondary data are collected such as newspapers, organizational website. Answers were obtained via structured interviews. Participants received an email through their private email addresses, and those who agreed to participate were invited to meet via phone, skype, WhatsApp and some of them emailed the answers. A script with open questions was used to conduct the interviews. This study was focused on investigating the mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of

marketing on Car purchasing Intention in Sri Lanka. This has used mostly primary data instead of the secondary data as the primary data deemed to be up to date while secondary data are old. When gaining more insights in relation to the research questions and objectives primary research data has been effective and helpful. When it often becomes difficult to collect relevant and accurate data from secondary sources, primary data sources have been used due to accessibility issues (Cerar et al., 2011).

4.7.4 Operationalization

Operationalization of the variables is explaining in the following table with clear explanation on the variables and measurement items.

Table 0-1: Operationalization of the variables

Source: Author Created

Variable	Indicator	Question Number	Measurement Scale	Literature			
Environmental Awareness	Knowledge	1, 4	Five point Likert Scale	(Tanwir & Hamzah, 2020)			
	Familiarity	2, 5					
	Clear selection	3					
Green Perceived Value	Value	6		Five point Likert Scale	(Esmaeili, et al., 2017)		
	Performance	7					
	Environmentally Friendly	8, 9					
Green Trust	Reliable	10			Five point Likert Scale	(Chen, et al., 2015)	
	Dependable	11					
	Trustworthy	12					
	Meeting expectations	13					
Brand Image	Identification	14, 18				Five point Likert Scale	(Khudri & Farjana, 2017)
	Familiarity	15					
	Recalling	16					
	Differentiation	17					
Purchasing Intention	Attitude	19, 20	Five point Likert Scale				(Tanwir & Hamzah, 2020)
	Likeness	21, 22					
	Confidence	23					

4.7.5 Data Analysis

In the research onion, data analysis together with the data collection have been identified as critical part. Data analysis is a process of evaluating the data analytically and logically and this is done every part of the data collected for the study (Moser et al., 2018). Process of data analysis classified for quantitative and qualitative data analysis processes. Quantification of the data collected from various sources is identified as quantitative data analysis. For these different statistical methods use to convert the raw data into understandable numerical presentations (Devi, 2017). For the qualitative data, verity of interpretations is used and as examples for the qualitative data analysis methods we could identifies such as thematic analysis, disclosure analysis, content analysis, narrative analysis etc.

In this study, researcher used both quantitative and qualitative data analysis used for the best use of qualitative data and quantitative data with the purpose of increase reliability and accuracy of the research. Blend of both analyses can positively contribute towards the achievement of research objectives and questions.

For the quantitative research part of this study, statistical methods are used as the data analysis method. SPSS statistical software and PROCESS tool are used in the present research to test the hypotheses and to reach the objectives. Furthermore, descriptive statistics, reliability analysis with Cronbach's Alpha method, correlation analysis with the Pearson correlation coefficient, and multiple linear regression method have been used in analysing the data and to test the respective hypotheses.

For the qualitative data, thematic Analysis was utilized. This process was used for encoding qualitative information and it worked to pinpoint and emphasize emerging themes through the examination of common patterns within the data (Boyotzis ,1998), otherwise known as coding. researcher began establishing a sense of familiarity with the data by thoroughly reading through the transcript number of times. I then proceeded to interpret anything which carried specific meaning and relevance to my research questions, thus preventing the risk of unimportant data. After close analysis of the transcript and my notations, I was able to construct codes into several different thematic categories; by doing this, there was less risk of my ideas overlapping. Once devised themes, they had to be comprehensively reviewed to ensure that they genuinely derived from the coding as well as the data set. It was also important to confirm that the themes

appropriately fit in to the data. I then selected fragments from the transcript to analyse, which assisted in creating a narrative -like underpinning. This is a process that is used to conduct an analysis of qualitative data. It is a generic approach to analyse people's reports that range from the basic to different kinds of qualitative interpretations (Percy, Kostere, and Kostere, 2015). Participants' experiences, motivations and ideas were critical for me to have understanding rather hidden and unspoken areas. Accordingly, interview transcripts were analyzed with the help of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Understand and note the patterns through initial categories after reading them several times. Relevant quotations were assigned to initial categories, and they were further refined as codes. The related method recognized quotations belonging to the same conceptual labels. Author has undertaken this process independently after having discussion and agreement on greater-level categories surrounding the initial coding.

4.7.6 Ethical considerations

Research ethics have been identified as principles and rules which notably contribute towards increasing the relevance, reliability, and validity of research findings. As the research is based on primary data there is a requirement to follow appropriate research ethics to maintain the confidentiality and security of the participants of the research. Researcher ensured that participants were informed about the objective of the study before performing the survey and interviews. Before the interviews, consent form sends and got the reply and then interviews were conducted and with regard to online surveys, it included written consent to fill before the survey. The personal details of the researchers were maintained confidentially. By following the rules and regulations of the Data Protection Act 1998 researcher took all ethical actions.

CHAPTER 5: FINDINGS

5.1 Quantitative research section

5.1.1 Chapter Introduction

The chapter is mainly focusing on the results and findings of the study. Firstly, descriptive statistics have presented to ascertain the data patterns and analysis of data that are explaining the acceptance and the rejection of the articulated hypotheses. Concerning the quantitative data analysis application, four hypotheses have been articulated in the study. Several statistical methods were used and applied in understanding and managing these hypotheses. A sample profile has been provided with the demographic variables and descriptive statistics are also provided in the chapter with an explanation of the summary of the variables. Further, reliability analysis has been done with Cronbach's Alpha value and further, Pearson Correlation coefficient has been used in correlation analysis. Multiple linear regression has been undertaken in the model development with the first three hypotheses testing and mediation of brand image has been tested with PROCESS tool in SPSS.

5.1.2 Sample Profile

It has been provided the sample profile has been examined and illustrated with several demographic variables. It is necessary to understand these demographic variables to have a clear understanding of the behaviour of the sample. Along with the behaviour pattern of the sample, it is counted that responses are also getting deviated and differed. Several stages have been tested here and these are age level, income level, marital status, and gender. All these variables are explaining the composition of the sample in a clear manner.

5.1.3 Age Level

Age of the respondents is provided in the following figure.

Figure 0-1: Age of the respondents

As per the age level of the respondents, majority has been recorded to be in the age group of 41 – 50 years and it is showing as 50.52 % with 194 respondents. Rest is in the age group of 31 – 40 years and it is showing 49.48 % and recording 190 respondents.

5.1.4 Marital Status

Marital level of the respondents is another important identification and this has been provided in the following figure. Marital level showed with two options as married and unmarried.

Figure 0-2: Marital status

As per the outcomes, it is showing that majority are married, and it is 62.76 % of the sample and recording 241 respondents. Unmarried percentage is showing as 37.24 % and it has recorded 143 respondents.

5.1.5 Gender

Following figure gives the gender of the respondents. It is showing that majority of the sample is male, and it has showing 63.54 % in the sample with 244 respondents. Female count has been showing as 36.46 % and it is recorded as 140 respondents.

Figure 0-3: Gender of the respondents

5.1.6 Income Level

It is very important to understand the income level of the respondents to make sure the purchasing intention is prevailing effectively. Accordingly, monthly income level has been provided in the following figure.

Figure 0-4: Income level of the respondents

Measures are provided with the LKR and monthly income. It has been recorded that majority of the sample has been identified with the income level of 15 000 000 – 20 000 000 LKR monthly. This is showing that sample is consisting 41.93 % in this group, and it has recorded as 161 in number. It has further recorded that 30.99 % of the respondents are having the income 10 000 000 – 15 000 000 LKR and it has showed with 119 respondents. 21.61 % of the sample is showing in the sample with the income more than 20 000 000 LKR monthly and it has recorded with 83 respondents. Moreover, sample is consisting with 5.47 % respondents, and it is consisting with 21 respondents as well. This group is having a monthly income of 500 000 – 10 000 000 LKR.

5.2 Descriptive Statistics

There are different magnitudes and ranges of the data points, and it is necessary to understand the behaviour of the variables which is necessary in making proper outcomes (Evans, 2019). Descriptive statistics are highly important and needed for better delivery of understanding about minimum values, maximum values, mean values, and standard deviation values of each of the variables (Mishra, et al., 2019). There are four variables presented in the research and each one has different variations in the measures. Environmental awareness is a critical application, and the minimum number here is 1 while the maximum number is 3.4. The mean value is 2.10 and the standard deviation is 0.761. The green perceived value variable is having a minimum value of 1.25 and a maximum value of 5 with a mean value of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 0.681. Green trust is another important identification, and it has a minimum value of 1.4 with a maximum value of 3.8. The mean value is 2.75 and the standard deviation is 0.613. Brand image is the next variable, and it has a minimum value of 2 and maximum value of 4.6 and a mean value of 3.57. Purchasing intention is another application and it has been recorded that the minimum value is 1.2 and the maximum value is 4.2. The mean value is recorded as 2.64.

Table 0-1: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics					
Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Environmental Awareness	384	1.00	3.40	2.1042	.76146
Green Perceived Value	384	1.25	5.00	3.8965	.68187
Green Trust	384	1.40	3.80	2.7578	.61384
Brand Image	384	2.00	4.60	3.5707	.75347
Purchasing Intention	384	1.20	4.20	2.6495	.90600
Valid N (listwise)	384				

5.3 Reliability Analysis

Reliability of the variables is counted as another application that is needed in understanding the application of the variables in data collection. Reliability is a necessary factor for the identification of the properties of measurement scales (Trizano-Hermosilla & Alvarado, 2016). It is mainly considered with the items that compose the scale. Reliability can be measured with several methods and the most common and highly used method in the reliability investigation is Cronbach's Alpha method (Bonett & Wright, 2015). Cronbach's Alpha method is referring to having alpha values for each of the measurement scales and this value can be ranging from 0 to 1. It has been recorded that the Alpha value needed to be more than 0.6 to have the accepted level of reliability (Bujang, et al., 2018). Alpha values that are greater than 0.7 have been recorded as the measurements having a higher level of reliability and alpha values that are greater than 0.8 are recorded to have a very higher level of reliability. Accordingly, understanding Cronbach's Alpha value is counted as very important to understand the level of reliability of the variables.

Results of the reliability analysis is provided in the following table.

Table 0-2: Reliability Analysis

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha value
Environmental Awareness	05	0.844
Green Perceived Value	04	0.669
Green Trust	04	0.828
Brand Image	05	0.853
Purchasing Intention	05	0.822

It has been recorded that the environmental awareness variable is having five question items and the Cronbach's Alpha value has been recorded as 0.844. This value is higher than 0.8 and thus, a very higher level of reliability can be recorded. The next variable is the green perceived value. It has four items and the Cronbach's Alpha value has been recorded as 0.669. This value is higher than 0.6 and thus, an acceptable level of reliability can be recorded. Green trust is the next variable and as per the outcomes, Cronbach's Alpha value is recorded as 0.828. This value is higher than 0.8 and thus, a very higher level of reliability can be recorded. Brand image is the next variable, and it has five items. Cronbach's Alpha value is recorded as 0.853 and this

is a value higher than 0.8 and thus, a higher level of reliability can be recorded. Purchasing intention is the next variable and there are five items in this variable. As per the results, the alpha value is recorded as 0.822 and this is a very higher value. Thus, a higher level of reliability can be recorded in this variable.

5.4 Correlation Analysis

Bivariate correlation is another important identification that is needed to be considered and identified in understanding the connection among the variables. The strength of the linear relationship between two variables can be considered with the correlation analysis (Zhu & Yuan, 2015). Further association among the variables is also considered by the correlation analysis at an effective level. There are different methods for testing the correlation analysis among the variables. One of the most famous methods can be considered the Pearson Correlation Coefficient method. This is considered with the Pearson Correlation Coefficient value with the significant p values. This value can range from +1 to -1 (Schober, et al., 2018). Negative values are referring the negative correlation among the variables. This is meaning that increasing one variable is resulting decreasing the other variable. Positive values are referring to the positive correlation among the variables. This is meaning that increasing one variable is resulting an increase in the other variable as well. This coefficient value is needed to be larger (Yang, et al., 2015). Further, a significant p-value is needed to be less than 0.05 to correlate with the variables in a 95 % confidence interval. With these measures, the correlation outcome of the variables is provided in the following table.

Table 0-3: Correlation analysis

Correlations					
		Environmental Awareness	Green Perceived Value	Green Trust	Purchasing Intention
Environmental Awareness	Pearson Correlation	1	.773**	.860**	.854**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.000	.000
	N	384	384	384	384
Green Perceived Value	Pearson Correlation	.773**	1	.826**	.223**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.000	.000
	N	384	384	384	384
Green Trust	Pearson Correlation	.860**	.826**	1	.858**

	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	384	384	384	384
Purchasing Intention	Pearson Correlation	.854**	.223**	.858**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	384	384	384	384
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

It has been recorded that the correlation between the two variables environmental awareness and green perceived value is positive and significant with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.773 and a significant p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between two variables in a 95 % confidence interval can be recorded. It has been recorded that the correlation between the two variables environmental awareness and green trust is positive and significant with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.860 and a significant p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between two variables in a 95 % confidence interval can be recorded. It has been recorded that the correlation between the two variables environmental awareness and purchasing intention is positive and significant with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.854 and a significant p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between two variables in a 95 % confidence interval can be recorded. It has been recorded that the correlation between the two variables green perceived value and green trust is positive and significant with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.826 and a significant p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between two variables in a 95 % confidence interval can be recorded. It has been recorded that the correlation between the two variables green perceived value and purchasing intention is positive and significant with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.223 and a significant p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between two variables in a 95 % confidence interval can be recorded. It has been recorded that the correlation between the two variables green trust and purchasing intention is positive and significant with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.858 and a significant p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, a positive and significant correlation between two variables in a 95 % confidence interval can be recorded.

Accordingly, the results are showing that correlation among the variables are positive and significant. As the Pearson Correlation Coefficient values are positive, and this is referring that increasing one of the respective variables is resulting the increment of the other respective

variable. It is clear that correlation has delivered the linear connection among the variables successfully.

5.5 Hypotheses Testing

Four hypotheses have been articulated in the study. Among these hypotheses, three hypotheses are showing the direct relationship while the last hypothesis is showing the mediation effect of the brand image. Understanding and identification of these hypotheses are very important for the better development of outcomes. These hypotheses are tested with the multiple linear regression method and PROCESS application. Some assumptions are needed to be tested and these assumptions are necessary to be identified at a clear level to make a better application of the outcomes. Along with this application, hypotheses are tested in the research with the application of the testing assumptions and other factors in a clear manner.

5.5.1 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regression is one of the methods that is used in the analysis of the connections between the independent and dependent variables. This is a method used in research by many scholars (Uyanık & Güler, 2013). Multiple linear regression is a widely used method and this is an easy method to use in analysing. Interpretations of the data and analysis are easy in the multiple linear regression application. Further, the robustness of the data is also one of the reasons that can be recorded as important in using this method by many scholars (Abuella & Chowdhury, 2015). Another important identification can be recorded as the ability to use different types of data in this analysis method. There are different types of data as time series data, panel data, and many more. Multiple linear regression is having the ability to use all these data in the analysis requirements (Nimon & Oswald, 2013). This method is a very important and necessary identification that can be used in the analysis and further, this has been used by the researcher in understanding the outcomes of the hypotheses testing.

a) Assumption Testing

Several assumptions are needed to be tested in the understanding of the multiple linear regression analysis applications. One of the assumptions can be recorded as the availability of more than one independent variable. To run multiple linear regression analysis, there should be more independent variables, and having one independent variable is referring to the simple

regression analysis. Here, three independent variables can be seen, and accordingly, it is clear that the assumption is accepted in the analysis (Asadi, et al., 2014).

Another assumption can be identified as the absence of autocorrelation. Autocorrelation is referred to the situation when the residuals are not independent of each other. Autocorrelation presence and absence can be identified with the Durbin-Watson value. As per the outcomes and explanations of the scholars, Durbin Watson's value is needed to have values between 1.5 and 2.5 to have acceptance of the assumption (Abuella & Chowdhury, 2015). Accordingly, Durban Watson's value in the present analysis has been recorded as 1.804 and this is a value between the said values of 1.5 and 2.5. Thus, acceptance of the assumption can be identified and recorded.

The next assumption of the multiple linear regression is considered the absence of multicollinearity. Multicollinearity is referred to the higher level of correlation among the independent variables. Once there is a very higher level of correlation among the independent variables, the assumption is violated, and multiple linear regression analysis cannot be applied. This measure has been tested in the past literature with VIF value. This is a value that is needed to be between 1 and 10 (Uyanık & Güler, 2013). When the values are higher than 10, the assumption is violated. Thus, the values are needed to be between 1 and 10 to accept the assumption. As per the results, generated, VIF values of the regression outcomes are showing among 1 and 10 and thus, the assumption is accepted.

Another assumption that is been recorded in multiple linear regression can be identified as the normality of the standardized residuals. It is a must to have the normality of the residuals, and this can be identified with the Normal P-P plot of standard residuals (Asadi, et al., 2014). The following figure gives this plot, and it is showing that the data points are situated near the line.

Figure 0-5: Normal P-P plot of standard residuals

As there is no deviation from the data points, acceptance of the assumption can be recorded. Another important assumption can be recorded as heteroscedasticity. The errors are needed to have the same but unknown variances. This is needed to be tested and once this is violated, the heteroscedastic nature of the data points can be seen (Asadi, et al., 2014). This is identified by the scatterplot and as per the outcomes, the following gives the scatterplot of the dependent variable and the regression standardized predicted values. As per the outcomes, it is showing that no patterns are showing but scattered. This is further explaining the acceptance of the assumption.

Figure 0-6: Scatterplot

b) Model Development

Multiple linear regression model can be developed and generated in a clear manner with the incorporation of the independent variables recorded as environmental awareness, green perceived value, and green trust. Results of the multiple linear regression analysis is provided in the following table.

Table 0-4: Multiple linear regression analysis results

Coefficients								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-1.348	.153		-8.833	.000		
	Environmental Awareness	.487	.051	.409	9.549	.000	.258	3.880
	Green Perceived Value	.239	.029	.180	8.221	.000	.989	1.011
	Green Trust	.741	.063	.502	11.738	.000	.259	3.862
a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Intention								

The results are clearly showing that environmental awareness in marketing applications can be impacted the purchasing intention of cars in Sri Lanka. This is shown by the positive and significant results of the relationship between environmental awareness and purchasing intention of cars. The beta value is showing as 0.409 and this is a larger and positive value. The t-value has been recorded as 9.549 and the significant p-value has been recorded as $0.000 < 0.05$. These measures are showing significant value and show the positive relationship between environmental awareness in marketing and purchasing intention of cars in Sri Lanka. By these results, acceptance of hypothesis one (H1: Environmental awareness in marketing is having a significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka) can be recorded in a 95 % confidence interval. There is empirical evidence showing that environmental awareness is highly impacting on the willingness to pay, subjective norms, attitude, and perceived behavioural control. The study has used the theory of planned behaviour and statistical analysis has been undertaken in the results generation. Health consciousness is another factor that has been found as a higher impact on purchasing green variables which are

counted as very important. Along with these identifications, it has been recorded that environmental awareness is impacting on green furniture purchasing and it is highly needed to understand the customer on the reasons for purchasing as well (Xu, et al., 2020). Accordingly, many literature applications are showing similar results among these two variables (Asif, et al., 2018; Suki, 2016; Indriani, et al., 2019; Sreen, et al., 2018; Jung & Seock, 2016; Hsu, et al., 2017; Tan, et al., 2017; Okada, et al., 2019).

It has been recorded that green perceived value is having a significant relationship with purchasing intention of cars in Sri Lanka. Green perceived value is a significant application in marketing. This has been focused on understanding influencing attitudes toward purchasing cars. The beta value is showing as 0.180 and this is a larger and positive value. The t-value has been recorded as 8.221 and the significant p-value has been recorded as $0.000 < 0.05$. These measures are showing significant values and showing positive relationships among the green perceived value in marketing and purchasing intention of the cars in Sri Lanka. In accordance with these results, acceptance of hypothesis two (H2: Green perceived value in marketing is having a significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka) can be recorded in a 95 % confidence interval. There is empirical evidence that are showing the connection between the two variables, and these are showing more significant relationships effectively. A study has been undertaken regarding the green benefits, green transparency on green perceived values, and green consumption. The study is showing the mediation role in the green perceived value among the relationships of green benefits, green transparency, and brand loyalty (Lin, et al., 2017). It is counted this is a very important consideration and the study has been undertaken in China Mainland. It is counted that the primary data has been used in the research and the data were collected from 826 respondents in China the statistical analysis has been undertaken in testing the necessary hypotheses in the study. It is showing that organizations are needed to have diversified green management applications and it is counted that usage of these applications makes better purchasing options for the customers (Lin, et al., 2017). Likewise, there are many such findings showing the similar outcomes effectively (Wu, et al., 2015; Ghazali, et al., 2017; Jamal & Sharifuddin, 2015; Trang, et al., 2019; Chaudhary & Bisai, 2018; Degirmenci & Breitner, 2017).

The third variable here is green trust in marketing. The connection between green trust and purchasing intention has been investigated and recorded here. Along with this identification, significant measures have been recorded and identified. The beta value is showing as 0.502

and this is a larger and positive value. The t-value has been recorded as 11.738 and the significant p-value has been recorded as $0.000 < 0.05$. These measures are showing significant values and showing positive relationships among the green trust in marketing and purchasing intention of the cars in Sri Lanka. By these results, acceptance of hypothesis three (H3: Green trust in marketing is having a significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka) can be recorded in a 95 % confidence interval. There is empirical evidence that are showing the connection between the two variables, and these are showing more significant relationships effectively. Drivers of green product adoption has been considered and it is necessary identification and manages better deliveries further, it is counted as a very important and needed to manage better identification of green product adoption for better delivery actions as well (Cheung, et al., 2015). The study has collected the primary data and 188 respondents were selected as the sample here it is further recorded that the green perceived value and the perceived quality are having direct and significant impacts on the green purchasing intention of the products while the green trust is showing a mediation among these relationships (Cheung, et al., 2015). At the similar time, the green trust is showing a relationship with the green purchasing intention as well which is counted as important. Likewise, there are many studies showing similar results and thus, connection among the green trust and purchasing intention can be recorded as positive and significant (Doszhanov & Ahmad, 2015; Nam, et al., 2017; Chen, et al., 2015; Wei, et al., 2017; Agmeka, et al., 2019). With these outcomes, regression model can be created, and this is showing as follows.

$$PI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EA + \beta_2 GPV + \beta_3 GT + \mu$$

Whereas;

PI = Purchasing Intention

EA = Environmental Awareness

GPV = Green Perceived Value

GT = Green Trust

β_0 = Intercept of the regression line

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = coefficients of the independent variables

μ = Standard error

The model can be created as follows.

$$PI = \beta_0 + 0.409 EA + 0.180 GPV + 0.502 GT + \mu$$

This is explaining that increasing one unit of environmental awareness in marketing can increase 0.409 units of purchasing intention of the customers in Sri Lanka. Further, increasing one unit of the green perceived value can increase 0.180 units of the purchasing intention of

the cars in Sri Lankan customers. Increasing one unit of the green trust can increase 0.502 units of the purchasing intention of cars in Sri Lankan customers.

Created model is needed to be tested for the model fit and this can be done in different methods. The most common and highly used method in the model fit investigation can be recorded as the R-squared method. R is the coefficient of determination, and the value is needed to be higher to have a proper model fit value. This is recorded in the following table and R squared value is recorded as 0.820. R squared value is explaining the variation of the dependent variable around its mean as explained by the independent variables. Here, it is explained that 82 % of the variation in purchasing intention is explained by the independent variables.

Table 0-5: Model summary outcomes

Model Summary										
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	
1	.906 ^a	.820	.819	.38570	.820	577.772	3	380	.000	1.804
a. Predictors: (Constant), Green Trust, Green Perceived Value, Environmental Awareness										
b. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Intention										

Another method of understanding and checking the model fit measures is recorded as ANOVA test. ANOVA is explaining the outcomes of F statistics. F value is needed to be higher and as per the outcomes, F value is explaining as 577.772 and the significant p value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Accordingly, model fit is further explained as accepted.

Table 0-6: ANOVA outcome

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	257.851	3	85.950	577.772	.000 ^b
	Residual	56.529	380	.149		
	Total	314.380	383			
a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Intention						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Green Trust, Green Perceived Value, Environmental Awareness						

Accordingly, first three hypotheses have been identified as accepted in 95 % confidence interval.

5.5.2 PROCESS Application (Mediation Testing)

Mediation of brand image is considered in the model in order to have clear understanding on the acceptance of the fourth hypothesis. Mediation has been tested with the PROCESS application. Considering framework for the mediation analysis has been provided in the following figure.

Figure 0-7: Mediation application of brand image

As per the figure, relationship A is explaining the direct relationship between eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention. Relationship B is explaining the connection between eco-friendly marketing and brand image. Relationship C is showing the connection between brand image and purchasing intention. The indirect effect of eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention is explained by both relationships B and C.

Understanding these relationships is very important and the results are provided as follows.

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
BI

Model Summary							
	R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
	.4751	.2257	.4407	111.3321	1.0000	382.0000	.0000
Model							
	coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	
constant	5.6272	.1978	28.4452	.0000	5.2382	6.0162	
M	.7044	.0668	10.5514	.0000	.8357	.5731	

Figure 0-8: Relationship eco-friendly marketing and brand image

As per the results, the beta value is showing as 0.7044 and this is a higher and positive value. Further, the t-value is 10.5514, and the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$. By these factors, it is clear that eco-friendly marketing is having a significant relationship with the brand image in a 95 % confidence interval. R squared value in this relationship is showing as 0.4751. Thus, the positive and significant relationships can be recorded.

The following figure gives the connection between eco-friendly marketing and brand image on purchasing intention of the cars. The collective impact of both variables is explained in this figure. The outcomes, it is showing that both variables are significantly related to purchasing intention. Eco-friendly marketing is having a significant relationship with purchasing intention with a beta value of 1.4626 and t value of 29.3426 and a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Brand image is having a significant relationship with the purchasing intention with a beta value of 0.1308 and t value of 3.8900 and a significant p-value of $0.001 < 0.05$. R squared value is recorded as 0.8772 and this is a higher value as well.

```

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
  PI

Model Summary
      R      R-sq      MSE      F      df1      df2      p
      .8772   .7694   .1902  635.7582  2.0000  381.0000  .0000

Model
      coeff      se      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant  -1.1535   .2295  -5.0260  .0000  -1.6048  -.7023
M          1.4626   .0498  29.3426  .0000   1.3645  1.5606
BI         .1308   .0336   3.8900  .0001   .1969  .0647

```

Figure 0-9: Connection among eco-friendly marketing, brand image and purchasing intention.

These results are showing that the indirect relationship between eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention is positive and significant. A direct relationship between eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention is also provided in the following figure which is explaining the clear relationship.

As per the outcomes, the beta value is recorded as 1.5547 and this is a positive and higher value. The t-value has been recorded as 34.8075 and the significant p-value is recorded as 0.000

< 0.05. These results are showing that a significant positive relationship is prevailing between the two variables. R squared value is recorded as 0.8719 and this is a higher value as well.

```

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
  PI

Model Summary
      R      R-sq      MSE      F      df1      df2      p
    .8719    .7603    .1973  1211.5612    1.0000   382.0000    .0000

Model
      coeff      se      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant  -1.8893    .1324  -14.2750    .0000   -2.1496   -1.6291
M          1.5547    .0447   34.8075    .0000    1.4668    1.6425

```

Figure 0-10: Direct relationship among eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention.

With these identifications, mediation impact of the brand image can be identified. Following figure is provided with the indirect, direct, and total effect of the relationship.

To achieve the mediation of brand image, the indirect effect needed to be significant. Relationships B and C have been accepted in the analysis and it is showing that the indirect effect is prevailing in the model. This outcome has been accepted in a 95 % confidence interval and thus, mediation has been accepted as the indirect effects are significant. The indirect relationship coefficient is another important measure that needed to be recorded and as per the figure above, this measure is 0.0921 which is positive. Further, BootLLCT and BootULCT values are also recorded as 0.0456 and 0.1435 and these are positive. These values are the upper and lower bounds of the relationship. As the values are positive and significant, the mediation impact of brand image can be recorded. Thus, hypothesis four (H4: Brand image is mediating the relationship between eco-friendly marketing and purchasing intention of the card among people in Sri Lanka) has been recorded as accepted in a 95 % confidence interval.

***** TOTAL, DIRECT, AND INDIRECT EFFECTS OF X ON Y *****

Total effect of X on Y					
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1.5547	.0447	34.8075	.0000	1.4668	1.6425
Direct effect of X on Y					
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1.4626	.0498	29.3426	.0000	1.3645	1.5606
Indirect effect(s) of X on Y:					
Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI		
BI	.0921	.0249	.0456	.1435	

Figure 0-101: Total, direct, and indirect effects

With the outcomes of the linear regression and mediation analysis outcomes, following summary table can be generated successfully.

Table 0-7: Hypotheses acceptance summary

Hypothesis	Measure	Acceptance and Rejection	Confidence interval
H1: Environmental awareness in marketing is having significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka	Beta = 0.409 T = 9.549 P = 0.000 < 0.05	Accepted	95 % confidence interval
H2: Green perceived value in marketing is having significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka	Beta = 0.180 T = 8.221 P = 0.000 < 0.05	Accepted	95 % confidence interval
H3: Green trust in marketing is having significant positive relationship with purchasing intention of the cars among people in Sri Lanka	Beta = 0.502 T = 11.738 P = 0.000 < 0.05	Accepted	95 % confidence interval
H4: Brand image is mediating the relationship between ecofriendly marketing and purchasing intention of the card among people in Sri Lanka	Indirect coefficient = 0.0921 BootLLCT = 0.0456 BootULCT = 0.1435	Accepted	95 % confidence interval

5.6 Primary Qualitative data analysis

Few key themes identified for each research objective and identified the related discussions based on the repetitive information gathered from the transcriptions. In this part of the chapter, analysis has been done using thematic analysis approach.

5.6.1 Environmental Effect and Car Industry

The increase of global private car ownership creates serious environmental risk and risk to human health and wellbeing. Therefore, this research was conducted to investigate the mediation effects of branding between eco-friendly aspects of marketing on car purchase intention in Sri Lanka. It has been found out that individual knowledge about environmental matters relates to green consumption and that knowledge are encouraged pro-environmental actions. Because most of the respondents have stated that they are having environmental concern and more likely to care about the environment through their consumption behaviours. Among all participants, majority of the participants answered positively on the questions about Eco friendliness in their car purchase decision except very few did not consider that.

5.6.1.1 Cost of the eco-friendly cars

Environment concerns of the consumers are increasing worldwide due to the changing environmental effects such as global warming, climate change, energy crisis and people in Sri Lanka also concerned about the environment as well. As it has discovered higher rate of pollution within the country it can be identified that there is a need of protecting the environment by using green products, less harmful items in their purchases through the patterns and profiles of the respondents. High costs involved with eco-friendly cars were disregarded by some of the respondents as they have recognized the criticality of those car purchase to have sustainable environment. People who earn higher income have also responded positively about the environmental effect in the choice of their personal car. Deputy Managing Director of a private company stated that he has selected an electric car rather than selecting fuel driven car due to the positive contribution that he could give to the environment. This is further evidenced by the quote: *“when we drive petrol/diesel cars, it is harmful because of the CO₂ emission. So,*

I have selected a car with a hybrid option even if it is a little bit expensive". And "Being a CEO of a multinational company, I could see that there is a higher potential to convert passenger cars to electric cars even if we have to pay additional price for additional benefits and protect our environment" (Participant 10). In fact, one of the respondents associated with car dealer company revealed that they focused on the green consumers positioning effectively as most of the people are price sensitive even when they choose environmentally friendly products. As such positioning strategy of the car dealer companies should be implemented carefully. In contrast, some of the respondents have not given priority to eco-friendly features and had negative intention about the high price charged. As such, people who could afford higher amount than those who do not tend to purchase eco-friendly cars. Being a developing country with economic crisis, majority of the people have been struggling to fulfil their basic needs. Therefore, people have started to think about the cost of vehicle by giving priority to the less expensive items in most of the time disregarding the environmental benefits. Financial factors weigh heavier in their decision making and respondents have not changed their conventional car to eco-friendly without financial favourability.

Participants were aware that there is a higher demand for passenger cars within the country which most people have considered the electric cars. But due to the high initial costs, people have usually bought less expensive cars even though they have high CO₂ emissions.

"I have seen that there are some electric cars on the road and there is a higher demand. But there are lot of diesel and petrol cars and other vehicles on the road compared to the electric cars" also from quote; "I can only afford a second-hand car which really fulfils my essential traveland it was a diesel car. I was not able to buy a car for a higher price even though I am an environmentally friendly consumer in my other purchases" (Participant-12) from another supportive quote "I do not believe that all people are considering the green concept when they purchase their car. Because it is expensive, and people must think about the cost rather than think about the eco-friendliness. (Participant- 16)"

The price and life of electric car batteries has been a major measurement when the customers choose whether to buy electric cars or not. Respondents have stated that *"there is no point in purchasing an electric car if the battery is going to depreciate sooner"* (Participant-8) which means customers mostly concentrated on other factors to select an electric car.

Similarly, the participants were most concerned about the fuel cost incurred together with the car price in their purchase of non-eco-friendly cars in their previous decisions of buying cars.

In contrast as the electric car option have eliminated gradually increasing fuel cost has also caused to turn their thinking about electric cars.

5.6.1.2 Age

In many cases respondents who were in the age of 25-35 stated that they have less considered about the environmental effects in purchasing their motor cars than those aged over 35. Majority of elder generation have thought about environment than younger people in the country.

In support of this analysis one of the interviewed consumers who was age 28 quoted: *“My main concentration was the price of car when I bought it. Because it was one of my dreams in life but to be honest, I had to wait till I save enough money to buy it. So, I didn’t care about the fuel emission impact as I was looking at a low price and a bit of high quality”* (Participant-14).

Few of the customers who married and got children stated that they always think about eco-friendly products as they think about a sustainable future for their children.

5.6.1.3 Urban areas

Some respondents who live in urban areas responded that they highly considered the effects of harmfulness while people who lived in the rural areas were less concerned about environmental harm. That is due to the negative experiences they have faced by living in a city rather than a village in Sri Lanka. This was evidenced by the quotes; *“We hear mostly noises coming from vehicles in the city where we live. That's horrible and carbon emission is the biggest issue, and we don’t have many trees in the city. That is directly linked to the most diseases, and I always buy eco-friendly items”* (Participant-17). Another respondent mentioned that *“We grew up in an environment where the people who used more environmentally friendly products, created less harm for the environment. Since my childhood I used greener products as a habit. So, I would like to buy my second car electric version of same brand as I love that brand”* (Participant-14).

5.6.1.4 Education

People who were selected with proper education stated that they focus mostly on environmental effects on their car purchase decision as they foresee negative results in the future in the context of the environment. This has been evidenced by quote; *“As a member of professional body I see the issue of environment pollution started with human negligence. If some people in part of the world adhere to the rules and regulations and protect the earth. But some are not specially in developing countries. I am happy that at least educated people like me nowadays moving to eco-friendly practices and. I am using an electric car as I do consider the environmental protection”* (Participant-16).

5.6.1.5 Government impact

Government tax policy on electric cars have encouraged some people to buy those cars. Taxes charged based on the emission of CO₂ for cars and based on the engine capacity and the age of car. Participants mentioned that it has discouraged them to buy petrol and diesel cars. Electric and hybrid cars got tax exemptions due to the less and zero carbon emission. These have resulted in increased demand for hybrid and electric cars. In supportive with that one of the respondents has stated that, *“I had to pay taxes at different points when I ordered my car and the usage of it. There were three different points like purchasing, annual tax for holding a CO₂ emission car and when I use the petrol on each time as an indirect tax and it’s expensive”* (Participant-04). Moreover, other taxes also discouraged most people buying conventional cars over eco-friendly cars. This was supported by the quote *“On the other hand, taxing based on the age of the vehicle will make the middle-class people pay more taxes on CO₂ emission cars than the rich using brand electric new cars and changing it frequently”* (Participant-15).

As many respondents stated the country has moved to importing electric vehicles and this approach has helped to prevent pollution. But that's a very small percentage compared to the other countries in the world. It has recognized that lot of countries in the world have moved to electric cars and awareness program need to be implemented within the country to have more knowledge on those cars. Their argument was less knowledge of the people about green cars and their technology. Majority of the participants stated that Sri Lankan government has granted subsidies on electric cars and other eco-friendly cars multiple ways such as tax incentives, capital grants for the local car assembly companies and those who promote the green car concepts. Evidenced by the quote *“electric vehicles are exempted, all other*

conventional vehicles including the state-owned vehicles are liable for the carbon tax” (Participant-20). In the year 2022, government proposal on electric cars have led migrant workers to import electric cars under very less will have some positive impact on the car market and for the environment as well. This has mentioned by government officer and supporting quote; *“In a bid to promote inward remittance, the government recently launched a program to allow migrant workers to import electric vehicles will be an advantage to environment”* (Participant-15).

Recent fuel price increased and scarcity of the fuel within the country have been positively affected the purchase of electric cars among the people as majority of the respondents mentioned. This can be identified as worldwide trend not only specific to one nation as the fuel generation, but CO₂ emissions also involved with the high environmental pollution.

Most of the respondents have mentioned that they are not ready to pay higher costs for the electric cars as hybrid cars due to the issues they have faced by using the electric cars such as difficulty of finding charging facilities, high costs of spare parts etc. In this situation, electric car usage has been reduced and environmental awareness has taken less priority.

5.6.2 Green marketing

Several car dealers together with their manufacturing companies have launched sever advertising campaigns to promote electric cars to the Sri Lankan market. As most of the agents have responded that it is an essential marketing technique to attract their sales. Majority of companies have been designed their marketing through their websites, different promotional activities in relation to green marketing to gain profitability.

As society become more concerned with the natural environment, some companies have been adopting to accept concepts such as waste reduction, environment management system. In many cases respondents mentioned that if they disregarded environment, it would cause long term sustainable issue. As a result, businesses have included environmental issues into organizational activities. One of the green marketing objectives were to achieve taking advantage of green opportunities utilizing their resources. In this case many respondents stated that there is a trend in the country with increasing pollution to protect the environment. Similarly, as many respondents stated that it is not only country’s expectation but also

globalized issue that people anticipated and emerged the need of protecting it. This explain that green marketing concept has help to take that opportunity to influence the consumers to purchase their products and services.

Many of dealer company respondents mentioned that adopting to verity of activities including improved advertising, changes to the production process, changing packages they have reached to the customers and change the mind to purchase green cars instead of conventional cars. Also, they have further stated that car manufacturing companies have adopted to the green marketing concepts by adopting to the above processes. Those processes have been delegated to their agents in Sri Lanka with instructions and procedures to follow. Respondents also mentioned that Integration of environmental sustainability into marketing has been adopted by their parent companies starting from beginning of the production of cars to after sales activities. Some of the respondents have stated that they have followed environmental protection procedures by communicating them to their customers and introducing green cars and green features to their cars. This has evidenced by the quote *“all the manufacturers sent the cars with the levels of emissions of new cars to identify the harm”* (Participant-06). This is one of the approaches that some consumers have attracted to the companies who followed the eco-friendly procedures. Moreover, some of the dealer company respondents mentioned that awareness program should be launched in the country to promote electric cars in the country to provide knowledge on those cars. Marketing communicates the product details and influence the people to buy their products which are unfamiliar. Therefore, in this circumstance car dealer companies have a huge responsibility to build up their marketing of green cars to increase the purchase intention. They have stated that awareness promotional activities already started by the parent companies and have directed them to promote them within the country. Green advertising has been always considered as an effective marketing tactic that can be applied to the promotion of services, goods, and business concepts. some of the small car companies based in Sri Lanka have taken the assistance from the well expert countries for manufacturing cars and they have advertised that to sale of their electric cars. For Ex: SK group has started to manufacture electric cars in the country with Korean assistance.

Respondents mentioned that some car dealers have done some donations to promote their eco-friendly car brands by emphasizing that they think not only about the environment but also of the people’s wellbeing. Supportive quote is; *“Toyota Lanka (Pvt) Ltd, extended our assistance to Sri Lanka’s fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, by way of a donation of two vehicles*

worth Rs 20 million. “also by quote, “*We have granted US\$ 10,000 from Ford Motor Company Fund to provide sustainable safe water sources for local residents in Uchchamunai islands*” (Participant-18). Indirect green marketing techniques such as schoolbook donation, scholarship programs have conducted by the respondents as an advertising. Similar type of CSR activities have been positively affected to the companies to attract eco-friendly consumers by creating positive brand image. However, some of the participants have stated that brand advertising hasn't been much effective when the prices of the cars higher and do not comply with their budget. These are cost-effectiveness and results. In many cases they have given the priority for the cost factor disregarding the advertising of eco-friendly cars. This is a situation which car dealers should pay higher attention to achieve both objectives through their effective green marketing strategy. Most of the respondents have mentioned that they would like to pay higher price for the green cars just because of the nature of adding value. Similarly cost of green cars has increased by adopting to the ecological policy measures and rules also affecting to their price. This explained that price is critical factor in green marketing in this industry.

As a way of green marketing some respondents stated that they have begun the concept with the manufacturing processes (used eco-friendly car manufacturing methods by parent companies), during the usage of the car (use renewable energy for the electric cars) and after usage processes (after sales services to enhance durability) have resulted to influences the potential customers. Companies always tried to enforce that they used renewable energy for production and recycled materials during the production processed and non-polluting as a safe practice of car manufacturers. This confirms one definition of green marketing which is a marketing strategy that aims to minimize the negative impact of a company's operations on the environment. Several of these companies have been seen to utilize their own websites and other promotional methods such as television and print advertising to convey the green marketing concept. In many cases, respondents stated that green marketing act as a background of first impression which the business tends to impress their customers/targeted audience to purchase eco-friendly cars. Since many other green marketing concepts have been designed to influence the customers, green marketing has the ability of increasing or decreasing the company success. This means that green marketing to be effective enough to attract and retain the customers and persuading them to adapt and encourage their purchase intentions. Participants also have mentioned that well-designed marketing campaign can make potential customers to stay for a long period of time keep them willingness in what company has to offer. Moreover, some participants stated that companies have invested lot of money on green marketing concepts to

become differentiate among the competitors. This is to achieve the purpose of attaining competitive advantage through green marketing.

Additionally, many respondents mentioned, and study has identified that, being a tourist attracted country, most of the time people have tried to maintain the clean environment with healthy biodiversity. This is another objective of green marketing through adhering to environmental advancements that kind of practices have built customers trust towards their green cars and positive consumers response have turned to purchase eco-friendly cars. In fact, one of the respondents mentioned that some companies misled the customers without delivering what they advertise through the marketing in the actual purchases. This shows that car dealer companies should take responsibility by being honest, transparent, and credible without misleading people. So that potential and target customers can attract to the companies and increase consumer base through an effective green marketing strategy.

Majority of the respondents have mentioned that they have almost integrated environmental sustainability to their marketing strategy to attract more customers in this industry. For Ex: car dealer companies have started environmentally friendly activities in various places in the country to influence people that those concerned with environment. This eventually starts building trust in potential customers and could be identified as one of the important considerations which companies contributing to the environment beyond their profit motivation. That was evidenced by the quote *“Serving the communities and protecting environment where we live, and work has always been important for Ford, and we are proud of our ongoing efforts and contributions that help provide real and long-term benefits to the people of Sri Lanka”* (Participant- 06). *On the other hand, we expect to attract more customers to our car brand through such awareness programs”*. maintaining such credibility has emerged as one of the most critical aspects of green marketing. This enables companies to attract potential consumers.

5.6.3 Online Advertising

Online Advertising is considered as an art of digital communication technique, and this is a medium of delivering marketing messages widely and comprehensively to a recognized intendent audience. This technique has largely helpful to the car dealer companies to promote the green marketing concept in Sri Lanka. Therefore, it can be implied from the responses

gathered from managers in Sri Lanka that online advertising strategy in green marketing has been designed to persuade purchase intention of existing and potential customers. In support of this analysis one of the interviewed authorize officer stated that *“Most marketers used digital marketing with the use of marketing tools such as social media, websites, mobile ads, mobile apps, emails and other digital platforms to connect the customers everywhere through the smartphones, tablets, computers, TVs and other digital devices to promote eco-friendly cars including other vehicles”* (Participant- 01). Therefore, it is necessary for companies to think about improving online advertising as a green marketing technique. This quote is also supportive for the above; *“automobile sector, along with banking and insurance, ecommerce, FMCG and consumer durables, has been the leading contributor towards digital advertisement in Sri Lanka”* (Participant-09).

In contrast, findings have identified that some barriers for the online advertising such as unavailability of suitable digital infrastructure within the country as per the view of a manager of a car dealer company.

Most of them expressed their opinions on social media and the mobile marketing advantages to their purchasing behaviour of motor cars. Consumers have not only connected within the country but also connected with the global to select the best purchase options. That’s the main advantage that most of the buyers within Sri Lanka have been benefited. Findings shows that that majority of Sri Lankan have not used online purchases and there was a fastest growth among the younger generation and the professionals. Even the authorized car dealers used some physical outlets island wide, some of the private car importers and few agents have only used the online platform to sell their motor cars. That has saved their money for using physical outlets in major cities, other overhead costs as mentioned by verity of respondents. In contrast, they have advertised their green products through digital marketing to convince purchase intention.

By analysing these important environmental aspects, an organization can develop from various viewpoints and take advantage of opportunities in terms of introducing new variations of products such as eco-friendly cars in Sri Lankan context. Through the responses, it can be interpreted that social media is a very effective marketing strategy that has facilitated brands to advertise, sell and enhance their productivity levels to a greater extent. Social media together with television media have become most effective channels through which customers gained information regarding products, prices and discounts made available by any brand. By sharing

blogs as well as success stories, some brands in the car industry have been able to promote their business.

CRM software and several effective green marketing research techniques are used as strategies by companies for sustainable growth of their businesses. Maintaining a proper customer relationship identified as tactic to increase the long-term sales effectiveness and marketing. Because it helps to retain and increase the customer base and ultimately bring positive organizational performances as stated by many of the respondents Strengthening brand image has been achieved as per them through high investment on CRM system with eco-friendly concepts. Proper CRM has attracted not only their existing customers but also potential customers. In supporting for that quote: *“we advertised developed responsive after sales service app which customers can now book a service for their electric cars, check the availability of spare parts and request a breakdown car from their mobile phone without visiting a showroom”* (Participant-18). Through advertising of after sale services most of the car dealers have attracted their sales of green cars creating confidence of customers to purchase from them. Respondents also stated that most of the manufacturers are offering their special upgrades, technological changes only through the authorized car dealers and it has been an advantage for them to advertise their motor cars to existing and potential customers. This is evidenced by the quote; *“The manufacturer nominates its local agent to act on their behalf and carry out pre delivery inspections and give warranty support, offer technical knowledge, in-house wheel alignment equipment and 24-hour breakdown services countrywide which will be useful for us to promote our car brand”* (Participant-06). This respondent has described usage of technology for improving their business profile in terms of increasing sales rates.

Some viewpoints of respondents describe the fact that online platforms are sometimes static in nature as the less developed technology. This might have limited chances for various car brands as being potentially adopt marketing strategies for the targeted customers, but these were simply not available. As per viewpoint of one respondent, it was recommended that promotion of some car brands through display print media has been considered appropriate. It became easier to connect with consumers to have an idea about green car supply and evaluate the needs via facilities offered from the internet. This is critical as it helps car brands to compete with other companies in the sector and achieve competitive advantage. This enables the long-term sustainability of the industry. Wide ranging options is made available for customers by different fashion brands and this feature has led brands to flourish in the competitive market

environment. Based on the response: *“We use CRM software to study consumer purchasing behaviours in the future”* (Participant-01). This respondent has delineated usage of technology for their business profile improvement and consequently increasing sales.

Appropriate pricing strategy has also maintained by brands to fulfil such requirements. As per customers’ purchasing behaviour, it has been clearly identified that certain groups of buyers preferred to purchase green cars, while others preferred to purchase conventional cars. Many customers have been highly attracted by product quality and affordable prices. Waste management has been critical to the car dealers as it need to be handled properly to mitigate the pollution and has led to enhanced customer base ensuing the businesses are environmentally responsible. Most car dealers in the industry of Sri Lanka have been expanded by utilizing numerous effective media as part of their marketing strategies. Social media was one of the marketing strategies that has helped these businesses to grow their position and meet requirements of consumers in the industry. Technical implementation has led most car brands to utilize different social media networks for marketing and selling. Thus, social media as crucial platform has benefited car dealer companies in car industry and enabled them to grow rapidly through increasing their customer base. One of the respondents from Toyota motor company mentioned that *“Company could achieve higher growth level when it achieved higher performances and the satisfied customer base. That is our success as a company”*. (Participant-18). This illustration has clearly mentioned that higher customer base for the company could achieve the growth of the company and increase the profit level. It has been examined from the managers responses that customer communication over online platforms such as social media accounts, emails, etc. has been relatively successful for attracting them towards eco-friendly cars.

However, some of the respondents mentioned that there are some disadvantages of using digital marketing to market the eco-friendly cars as evidenced by the quote; *“Most of the people are not using digital marketing to purchase a car in this country. That is because of unavailability of digital infrastructure facilities”* (Participant-20). This means that digital infrastructure facilities have been obstacle to eco-friendly car advertising for the car dealers as well as the consumers. Moreover, some respondents mentioned that they consider buying a car is one of the critical investments in life in this country and will need to have a face-to-face conversation with the car dealers rather than going through online platforms to make decision on that. In support for that quote *“It was a big investment in my life, and I had to meet several dealers to*

select the best car for me. I am not an online person,”(Participant-08) and also from the quote; *“I am not trusting the online media and I have never used it to purchase expensive items such as car, electric equipment etc”* (Participant-17). In fact, some participants have mentioned that people are still using personal selling, Telemarketing, catalogue marketing and newspapers which make motor car dealers face difficulties when they are promoting through the digital marketing platforms especially eco-friendly cars. This was evidenced by quote; *“I am not a fan of digital technological items as I don’t like to be addicted to my phone or my laptop. I usually look for car advertising pages of newspapers, watch TV and sometimes I get brochures from the dealers to find details I need. So, I am happy with that”* (Participant-08). Moreover, some of the respondents also mentioned that comparability could be done when they use the digital platform to purchase their eco-friendly car due to the availability of information.

5.6.4 Attitude about new Technology

However, some respondents hold various traditional attitudes towards newly invented products due to lack of information. It could be identified that those people were not willing to buy electric cars until they get confidence about electric cars. Similarly, inability find the relevant car parts have also affected for the less confidence in the ecological cars. This is confirmed by majority of respondents who have bought ecofriendly cars. Therefore, car dealers should make sure to maintain sufficient level of spare part availability and to ensure that they have dedicated to fulfilling the customers’ requirements in these types of greener cars. This will enhance the green trust among existing and potential customers. Respondents mentioned that electric and hybrid cars are not cheaper to run even they could buy them for a lesser price. Higher cost for the electricity, unavailability of charging facilities within the country have resulted to increase the fear of purchase of those cars. Some participants have mentioned that lack of investment from the government and private sector have resulted to lack of infrastructure facilities. Not everyone having individual charging points as per the economic situation of the country, but public charging points have helped to people to charge their EVs. Therefore, there is a need of investment in widespread charging infrastructure and eventually starts building trust in potential customers.

Car dealers have taken consideration to promote electric cars by promoting awareness programs among the people. It has increased the brand popularity and the sales. This means that dealer companies should effective enough in attract and maintain the attention of the

customers and encourage them to adopt their purchase intention. As per the interviewees, they have stated that they prefer the advanced technological gadgets which comes with the electric cars such as automated parking system, voice system etc. over traditional cars and those have allowed them to handle the car easily and has been positively influenced towards purchasing an electrical car. That was evidenced by the quote; *“Batteries provide cost-efficient overnight storage in electricity systems that increasingly depend on solar and wind sources. That in turn, will deliver the lower carbon intensity required to make EVs good for the planet.”* (Participant-02). Similarly, many of other respondents stated that eco-friendly features of world recognize electric car brand perceived the quality and those brands have attracted majority of them. This is evidenced by quote; *“Tesla vehicles are powered completely by electricity; their lifetime emissions are significantly lower. Tesla also provides an opportunity to generate solar energy through solar panels and store them in a Powerwall battery.”* (Participant-10). This means the car attributes which contribute positive environmental benefits have impacted for the purchase of green cars. It can be identified as one of the green marketing strategies which car dealers could earn competitive advantage over others. Sufficient infrastructure facilities required for the electric cars should implement by the state as a necessary step to facilitate consumers in long run. This was evidenced by the quote: *“Of course, EVs come in different types and sizes, and the bigger the electric car you buy, and the more you show off its superior acceleration, the greater the danger that the immediate impact of going electric will be an increase in emissions. Unfortunately, current EV offerings are skewed toward larger cars and SUVs, with fewer small and mid- size models, which will eventually deliver the biggest emissions reductions. This reflects the car companies’ profit incentives, the difficulties of achieving adequate range with smaller batteries, and the lack of sufficiently widespread charging infrastructure. But the charging infrastructure can and must be built, and a wider range of auto sizes will increasingly be available”.* (Participant-11)

Few respondents who were in management level of branded car selling companies mentioned that they are keen to import electric cars to get the advantage of the sunshine about 35 degrees almost during the year. This has been identified as one of the promotional methods which companies could influence customers effortlessly. This was evidenced by the quote; *“Sri Lanka should focus on the electric car, with sunshine we get all throughout the year, car solar batteries fitted to electric engines can be charged at no cost and it will also save fuel.”* (Participant-10).

When interviewees were asked about the present situation of the car industry all have mentioned that it has been highly competitive and challenging due to the current economic downturn in the country. For instance, one respondent has stated that: *“There are numbers of car dealer companies and brands in the market with high quality”* (Participant-09). This indicated that increasing competition has led different car brands to sell high quality eco-friendly cars in the market to retain potential and actual customers. likewise marketing strategy should be effective to attract customers and establish a competitive edge for brands in the market. Similarly, due to the perceived quality of the eco-friendly cars most of the consumers have turned to purchase them and it has been identified from the responses. Evidence can be cited from interview responses for supporting the fact that a competitive edge exists in relation to marketing strategies: *“with the increase of various car brands huge liability on our company to meet the customers expectation and as a result at any time our position might get affected”* (Participant-06). It has been repeatedly identified from the response analyses that competition with the car market has increased and will continue to increase with frequent changes in the choices of consumers. Failure to communicate the specialty of eco-friendly cars and benefit having them have resulted to significant drop in sales and market loss. Brand image, brand love and different choice of brands have been elements contributing towards growth in competition within the car industry. Due to these choices of brands most car companies focus on maintaining a portfolio of high-end brands like Tesla, BMW, etc. Another aspect highlighted by respondent was: *“if we fail to market our green car brand properly, they will turn to buy some other brands”*. It has become important for different car brands to analyse such factors for meeting customers’ requirements to compete with other brands. Without promotion of eco-friendly nature of the brand, it becomes difficult to attract customers as it makes a path to switch to other car types and brands. Differing choices and preferences of customers should be analysed by car brands before introducing them into the market. Analysis and identification of changing preference of the target customers are essential to create opportunities and increase the profit. Beyond the traditional marketing, expanding of businesses’ there is a huge responsibility of marketers to interacts with the natural environment and it is essential to maintain their relevancy and become an agent of change in order to achieve sustainable future.

6. CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION

6.1 Interpretation of descriptive statistics

The effect of eco-friendly services on potential car purchases in Sri Lanka has been studied. In this study, the branding's mediating function was also examined. For meaningful results to be produced, it is crucial to understand how these variables are related. This was developed and presented based on the measures of the quantitative analysis. According to the framework created, hypotheses were developed. This is merely dependent on the literature. Multiple pieces of literature that are crucial for the achievement of the objectives support the framework. Multiple linear regression and the PROCESS macro in SPSS are being used in the study to test each hypothesis. This is important for comprehending the main goal of the study. The development of a conclusion has been done in accordance with the goals and outcomes of the quantitative analysis.

The study's method of analysis was distinctive. Different variables were presented in the eco-friendly environmental factors. The most crucial characteristics, including environmental awareness, green perceived value, and green trust, have been used in the study. These are essential for comprehending the intentions behind the purchase (Okada, et al., 2019). Numerous studies have revealed various elements that may influence consumers' purchasing intentions, and these have been cited in various works of literature as the most significant results (Rahim, et al., 2016; Zhuang, et al., 2021; Sakar, et al., 2019). Due to the significance of the chosen variables, the results are noteworthy. Thus, it is apparent that the research made use of distinctive features when creating the objective. The results of the analysis show the mediation impact of PROCESS macro. This demonstrates how brand image has a significant impact on consumers' purchasing intentions. While effectively developing its results, the study is paying close attention to these actions.

The statistical analysis has been successful in achieving objectives, answering research questions, and testing hypotheses. In any country, consideration of the environment is important when purchasing a car. People are putting more of an emphasis on the creation of environmentally friendly applications when dealing with goods and services (Okada, et al., 2019). This is comparable to buying a car. People are becoming more conscious of the

environment. Globalization and industrialization are the main causes of this. Using the findings of the research, we primarily aim to comprehend and embed environmental awareness (Xu, et al., 2018). The first objective is to understand the impact of environmental awareness on car purchasing intentions in Sri Lanka. This is compatible with the first hypothesis as well. The first hypothesis seeks to ascertain the connection between Sri Lankans' intentions to buy cars and marketing's emphasis on the environment. A well-known technique for examining the relationships between the independent and dependent variables is multiple linear regression. The dependent variable in this situation was purchasing intention, and the independent variable was environmental awareness. The majority of the positive and noteworthy accomplishments of this connection are documented in earlier literature (Xu, et al., 2020; Asif, et al., 2018). As a result, the current study also investigates how these two variables are related. The t value is 9.549 and the beta value is found to be 0.409. Both values are higher and in the positive range. This demonstrates that the variables do indeed have a positive relationship. As a result, there is a positive correlation between environmental awareness and intention to buy a car. Another important consideration is the significance level of this relationship. This measurement has a large p value. It has determined the p value to be 0.000. With a 95% confidence interval, this value is less than 0.05, indicating that the relationship is significant. These statistical findings show a strong and positive correlation between environmental awareness and intentions to buy a car. Consequently, a confidence interval of one in the hypothesis' acceptance is noted.

Numerous findings from earlier literature can be used to demonstrate the success of this hypothesis. Since it has been determined that CO₂ emissions significantly contribute to global warming, electric vehicles are more suitable for preserving the environment. In Japan, this idea is widely used. A survey of electric car owners in Japan was conducted to learn more about their environmental consciousness and their plans to buy cars there. The study used structural equation modelling to analyse the relationships and found that people who buy electric vehicles are more environmentally conscious. Additionally, it demonstrates how environmental consciousness directly affects Japanese consumers' intentions to buy cars (Okada, et al., 2019). Another research has mainly targeted the understanding of the purchase intention of green cars in Malaysia and the understanding of environmental awareness. The subjective norm, perceived behavioural control, attitude, and the nation's level of car purchases that are environmentally friendly are some other factors that come into play. These connections have been clarified using structural equation modelling. Individual preferences were found to be unrelated to the intentions to make purchases. The purchasing decision is, however, influenced

by a wide range of other factors, including environmental awareness, attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioural control techniques. Consequently, to produce successful results, it is essential to understand these influencing factors (Afroz, et al., 2015). Likewise, many literature findings support the acceptance of the present research hypothesis one (Asif, et al., 2018; Suki, 2016; Indriani, et al., 2019; Sreen, et al., 2018; Jung & Seock, 2016; Hsu, et al., 2017; Tan, et al., 2017; Okada, et al., 2019). Accordingly, it comes as critical to understand this connection to gain effective results.

The second hypothesis in the research has been identified as “Green perceived value in marketing is having a significant positive relationship with the purchase intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka”. Green perceived value is the expected amount of the advantages and outcomes that consumers receive and the expected amount of the outcomes. These expectations and levels should be reached by the manufacturers and sellers to improve the outcomes. According to this, the green perceived value should be as high as possible in order to satisfy the customer (Lin, et al., 2017). The customer expects the environment to be harmed as little as possible. This outcome needs to be satisfied with the products and services (Lam, et al., 2016). The relationship between green perceived value and purchasing intentions is effectively identified. As a result, the current study also looks at how these two variables are related. The t value is 8.221 and the beta value is found to be 0.180. Both values are higher and in the positive range. This demonstrates that the variables do indeed have a positive relationship. As a result, there is a positive correlation between green perception and intention to buy a car. Another important consideration is the level of significance of this relationship. This measurement has a large p value. It has determined the p value to be 0.000. With a 95% confidence interval, this value is less than 0.05, indicating that the relationship is significant. According to one study, green product purchases in Brazil have increased due to factors such as green trust and green perceived value. The price elasticity and perceived value of green have both been considered in this study. Even though customers are more eager to buy environmentally friendly goods, the development of these green-related factors spurs on greater environmental preservation efforts. This has a significant impact on environmentally friendly consumer choices. In addition, it has been discovered that how valuable green is perceived varies from product to product. Therefore, in order to achieve the best results, proper understanding of this is required (De Medeiros & Ribeiro, 2016). It has been determined that increasing the perceived value of green is required to increase the purchase of green products. A study was conducted to investigate the purchasing intentions of green foods. The study is a

primary research study that has considered a number of variables, including conditional value, social value, and functional value. The perceived value of green is determined by each of these elements. 300 respondents were the target group for the data collection process. Results are significant and indicate that purchasing green foods successfully depends heavily on one's perception of their value (Woo & Kim, 2019). Many pieces of literature highlight the importance of the perceived value of green. This is a highly debatable topic. The present study's hypotheses considered the green value's perceived importance in producing noteworthy results. It is highly explained that green perceived value is necessary consideration for better developments in purchasing intentions of the products in the present era (Wu, et al., 2015; Ghazali, et al., 2017; Jamal & Sharifuddin, 2015; Trang, et al., 2019; Chaudhary & Bisai, 2018; Degirmenci & Breitner, 2017).

The third research hypothesis focuses primarily on green trust. Green trust is the choice a customer makes about a good or service based on how well it performs and how well it can protect the environment (Cheung, et al., 2015). This is an extremely important consideration for environmentally conscious customers (Amin & Tarun, 2020). Any product or service's purchasing behaviour and intentions can be influenced by green trust. Today's world is undergoing change. It is constantly evolving, making it necessary to take the results into better consideration (Al-Quran, et al., 2020). Thus, hypothesis three has been articulated as "green trust in marketing is having a significant positive relationship with the purchase intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka". Statistics have been used in the current study to investigate how to understand this connection. The hypothesis testing is related to some statistical variables. According to the findings of multiple linear regression analysis, Sri Lankan consumers' intentions to buy cars and their level of green trust are positively and significantly correlated. The beta value is determined to be 0.502 and the t value is 11.738. Both numbers are higher and fall into the positive territory. This proves that there is a strong correlation between the variables. The intention to purchase a car and green trust are therefore positively correlated. The degree of significance of this relationship is a further important factor to consider. The p value for this measurement is high. The p value was found to be 0.000. This value is less than 0.05 with a 95% confidence interval, demonstrating the significance of the relationship. Therefore, it is important to note that the hypothesis that the green trust has had an effect on purchasing intentions is accepted. Numerous earlier studies have produced comparable outcomes. It is important to comprehend this earlier literature. Research has demonstrated the influence of perceived quality and green trust on buying intentions. In this

study, environmental consciousness has acted as a moderator. 306 Pakistani consumers were considered during the research's conduct. The sample was chosen using a simple random sampling method. In order to analyse the outcomes, statistical methods have been used. According to the study, "green" trust, "green" risk, and "green" perceived quality are the primary predictors of consumers' intent to purchase. Further, environmental awareness is moderating the relationships effectively. (Wasaya, et al., 2021). The factors influencing the adoption of green products have been identified by another study. When buying the products, it's important to be aware of these factors in order to support green development. 188 participants were chosen for the study, and they provided data for the analysis of the research. For the outcomes to perform better, a number of factors, including green perceived value, green trust, and green quality, were thought to be essential. It went on to explain how consumer purchasing intentions are directly impacted by perceived green value and quality. Knowing the essential elements of green purchasing enables marketers to offer these in order to effectively satisfy customers (Cheung, et al., 2015). To encourage purchasing intentions, it is essential to comprehend the results of green trust. Furthermore, it is noted that consumers who care about the environment and who choose to buy products differently need to have green trust. There are numerous studies that have produced results that are consistent with the study's hypothesis (Doszhanov & Ahmad, 2015; Nam, et al., 2017; Chen, et al., 2015; Wei, et al., 2017; Agmeke, et al., 2019).

The current study makes use of brand image mediation. Purchase intentions are significantly influenced by brand image. Factors like "green trust," "green perceived quality," and "environmental awareness" can be important to customers (Tariq, et al., 2017; Hien, et al., 2020). Within meaningful confidence intervals, these factors were thought to have an effect on purchase intentions. Brand image has the potential to influence and mediate all of these relationships (Lee & Lee, 2018). Brand awareness and trust are provided to the consumer. This is how a particular product or service within the company is perceived by the customer. In order to deliver the results, it is necessary to comprehend the brand image level and green development factors. Consumers may have different perceptions of a brand. To deliver the desired results, organizations must work to enhance their brand image. The study has looked into how PROCESS macro mediated brand image. The findings demonstrate a direct link between eco-friendly marketing and consumers' intentions to buy. Additionally, it demonstrates that these factors indirectly influence one another through brand image. As a

result, brand image affects how much consumers will spend. Companies must comprehend these elements in order to encourage customers' purchase intentions.

According to research, brand image is important at various stages to encourage purchasing intentions. In one study, both greenwashing and purchasing intent are considered. In this case, brand loyalty's mediation has been considered. Taiwanese consumers who have purchased eco-friendly products have been considered for the research, and a sample has been drawn from them. Investigations into the potential negative relationships between greenwashing and purchasing intentions were conducted. Additionally, brand image and consumer brand loyalty to the company have been found to mediate the relationship (Chen, et al., 2020). Accordingly, different literature is showing the similar type of results supporting the hypothesis results in the present study. Understanding the brand image is critical factor for better development in the purchases (Chen, et al., 2017; Bukhari, et al., 2017; Butt, et al., 2017).

All of the hypotheses are supported by the study's findings within a 95% confidence interval. It is significant that factors influencing purchasing intentions include green trust, environmental awareness, and perceived value. In the auto industry, green marketing, also known as eco-friendly marketing, is important for making wiser decisions. Customers prefer to buy vehicles that have little negative environmental impact. The current customer has a higher level of environmental consciousness. Furthermore, brand image is considered. Before making a purchase, consumers must take the brand's reputation into account. Automobiles are high-end products, so research should be done before making a hasty purchase. As a result, it becomes crucially important to manage green marketing to inform consumers about the environmentally friendly effects of products. Through statistical analysis, the study effectively delivered the results. As a result, the 95 percent confidence interval identified all the hypotheses as being true. Additionally, previous literature backed up each of these conclusions. Green trust, green perceived quality and the environmental awareness are necessary factors in green marketing actions. Organizations should pay more attention towards these factors.

6.2 Justification of the neutral responses

Neutral opinions have been seen from the many participants of the research about purchasing of eco-friendly cars. Participants showed willingness to purchase the electric cars including other eco-friendly cars in the future which might adeptly protect car market in the country. Further this ensure that eco-friendly aspects marketing has chances of influencing purchase decision of green cars and eventually success the car dealers and protect the environment. That point mostly related to both the car dealers and for the consumers who participated in this research process. In terms of the gender, male respondents were contributed mostly than female participants. As per the marital status of respondents, the research observed that most of the population were married, which implied that participants had their concerns about environments once they have certain responsibilities of their lives and able to invest larger money on a car when they have cumulative savings.

Also, age group were selected between 31-50 to obtain reliable information from different perceptions. There was a presence of young age and old age members of the population, who demonstrated willingness in sharing opinions related to eco-friendly aspects of marketing, environment awareness and brand image, purchasing intention, etc., towards car dealers' companies and brands. Respondents who had employments were participated including students, retired people, professionals, and businesspeople who engage in the car industry in Sri Lanka. Majority of the respondents were observed to have monthly gross income of LKR 10Mn to 20Mn and few had yearly gross income between 500,000 to 10Mn.

6.3 Interpretation of qualitative data

6.3.1 Importance of Green marketing strategy

Study found that companies have taken advantage of utilizing the opportunity of the environmental protection expectation of the people by utilizing their resources to launch green marketing activities. This has been an advantage for those car dealer companies to influence the people who interested of buying them. Similar literature found as the Olson (2008) highlighted importance of developing practices to secure environment and consequently build the company's reputation. When firms producing superior quality products, using credible advertising, acting in a socially and environmentally

responsible manner and meet various stakeholder interests tend to create reputational advantage and that affect to influence potential customers (Miles & Covin, 2000).

Marketing environmentally friendly products was called green marketing according to the American marketing association 1975 definition. As such manufacturers adoption to the green marketing concept begin with the production process till the disposal of the products after usage (Pavan Mishra & Payal Sharma,2010). Accordingly, we have found that the green marketing of the cars has been started from the point of car manufacturers till the car owners disposed them in a way that protect the environment. In this scenario, car dealers have taken strong advertising to make awareness among the people about green car features and have communicated that manufacturer's green concepts to promote the eco-friendly cars in Sri Lanka. Some car dealers have mentioned that manufacturers have used recyclable spare parts, green energy to production of cars and ultimately those will minimize the pollution. In a study conducted in India to analyses the green marketing has found that organizations used their green practices through products, processes and by communicating that they have increased the business performance and it is a responsibility of both consumers and companies which is similar finding to the current study (Mayakkannan, 2019). Another literature found that transparent green marketing practices also have helped to promote corporate image and consequently have resulted to increase their products purchase (Singh and Pandey, 2012). Therefore, buyers have tendency to purchase products from a firm with green practices and it is their responsibility to maintain such level of eco-friendly processes and systems without limiting to the green products offered to the market. Furthermore, we could see that there is an essential requirement to invest in well-designed green marketing campaign to convey their genuine practices to potential customers to stay for a long period of time. Additionally trust built through the above practices has been affected to enhance consumer attraction to ecological cars and being honest, transparent, and credible without misleading people is a responsibility of firms introducing green cars to the market.

6.3.2 Importance of social media marketing as marketing strategy

The research study properly met qualitative empirical research requirements, due to the successful investigating verity of variables directly by communicating with people connected with Sri Lankan car market. Hence through systematic research, it was able to find relationship with the car dealer companies with online advertisements and hold an effective green marketing strategy of green car brands. As per the findings, online advertising has considered as an effective marketing strategy for the promotion of green cars and most of the managers of the car dealer companies have agreed with the criteria which they need to be followed to be succeed in the market. Green car brands and offers promotion through Facebook and other social media has been achieved and sending emails to the inbox of the customers including descriptive details of green features have used by car dealers. As per the many respondents this method of green marketing has been a necessity of the car market to influence purchase intention of the customers. As per the results found from another research conducted in more than 20 developing countries, it has found that compared with US, people who were in the emerging countries have mostly used the social media and relatively advanced in their usage of it. Therefore, it has been positively affected to electronic word of mouth and distribute information through social media about their products which certain customers have purchased their products with that information rather going for other conventional advertisements (Pew, 2015). This has been identifying as way of making car purchase by comparing each green car brands available in different marketplaces in Sri Lanka such as Ikman.lk, pricelanka.lk etc. Almost all the eco-friendly car brands have now used online marketing to target their customers and sell green cars. Another literature found in the study conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina has concluded that likes, shares, user comments, posts the brand promotes on their social media sites significantly impacts the distribution of information about the specific brand and online recommendations have extremely impacted to customer purchase decisions (Poturak, and Softic, 2019). However, selling and promotion of online have been affected to less people in the stores, manual cash transactions this is very important for the companies to implement their operations for boosting their future performances.

6.3.3 Online/Digital advertising

As a part of green marketing actions, advertising of auto brands play crucial role against our deteriorating environment, these auto-ads promote the consumption of nature friendly private cars. As per the research findings, natural imagery displayed in the advertisements have been influenced to purchase green cars and this has addressed how images of the advertisements and new contributed to people perception of nature. Respondents mentioned about the memorable advertisements for eco-friendly cars published in social media and television For Ex: outdoor adventure with their family members in an electric car showing happy family life through urban and rural environments have represented the many people's expectations in the country. Even though cost involved in electric car people have shown their willingness to purchase due to the influential effect of commercial adds. Therefore, marketing managers have immense responsibility to increase the potential customers through the advertisements. It has been determined that value of eye-catching attractive advertisements with high level of green marketing are prompted to purchase of electric cars in a similar study conducted in China (Chen, S., 2016). In fact, social media has been taken priority in the current practice of green marketing which is digitalization rather conventional advertising methods which was mentioned above. Therefore, companies should be mindful and take necessary steps to enhance the digital marketing including social media marketing over conventional advertising methods. The broad range of consumers utilizing social networks means that most target markets can be reached (Cha 2009). Another study investigated that consumers have been using social media (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, MySpace, and LinkedIn) and depended on them for marketing shopping decisions; promotion via these media has become critical. (Shankar et al. 2011, Bala, and Verma, 2018)

6.3.4 Corporate Social Responsibility

As a promotional activity of car dealer companies, they have adopted to the CSR practices to influence the purchase intention by improving brand image. Furthermore, various types of promotional activities required to attract customers to eco-friendly products. Therefore, implementing kind of CSR activities wisely is one of the critical responsibilities of the manager of brand or the organization. Similarly, to promote the eco-friendly car brands this could be identified as one of important consideration. These findings comply with the literature which

found that CSR actions is highly affected on the purchase intention and it as very important to manage the proper brand image in making the successful delivery actions in strategy development (Lee & Lee, 2018). Consequently, CSR has affected to enhance the firm's reputation as mentioned by some respondents and have found in the similar past research (Tiziana Russo-Spena , Marco Tregua , Alessandra De Chiara, 2016). . Additionally, electronic word of mouth also has been effective to enhance the purchase intention as it has identified by research conducted to prove brand image is mediating to for the purchase intention (Tariq, et al., 2017). Country of origin and the production manufacturing plants of the green cars have also been considered in the consumers purchases. This has been a practice for the conventional cars without limiting to the green car purchases. Identification of the brand images decided based on their product origin has directly impacted to influence purchase intention. Similar kind of research has been conducted to prove that brand image of a household appliance and companies have been able to increase their sales through influencing purchase intention (Hien, et al., 2020).

6.3.5 Impact of environmental awareness and eco-friendly car purchase

As shown by this study that environmental awareness, shows a significant influence on the intention to purchase an eco-friendly car playing an important role in influencing individuals' intention to purchase a green car. This is consistent with the literature which was conducted in Japan. People who have thought about the environmental benefits using the electrical vehicles had a positive intention to purchase them (Okada, et al., 2019). Findings recognized that carbon emission discharged to the environment has caused adverse effects to the air pollution and people have seen that climate changes and adverse impact to the urban cities. As such people managed to purchase their energy efficient cars with minimum carbon emission to atmosphere. This is consistent with the literature which shown that consumer's the environmental awareness has impacted on the green furniture purchasing and it is highly needed to understand the customer on the reasons of the purchasing (Xu, et al., 2020). In contrast, limited knowledge regarding the environmental protection has found as a barrier among people to eco-friendly purchase behavior. Most individuals were unfamiliar with hybrid and electric cars and their knowledge were limited, most of them were inexperienced and clueless on its potential benefits and long-term running costs. This has led to negative attitudes among individuals on the evaluation of whether to purchase green technology vehicles. As the literature found when people have no more understanding about the electrical vehicles than other vehicles, they don't

tend to buy electrical vehicles and are more likely to purchase traditional vehicles (Heffner et, al., 2007).

Consumer's green practices such as buying all the products related to the green, willingness to pay higher price for those green products have also affected to increase the purchase intention of eco-friendly car among the people. Moreover, the premium price of eco-friendly cars as compared with conventional cars also caused positive attitude of individuals towards the adoption decision, which value the green attributes presented by those vehicles. Similarly a literature found that Customers who buy more eco-friendly cars, think that it save their money in future and achieve sustainable future while protecting their prestige due to the higher price paid for hybrid cars (Jason and Lee, 2010).

Hence, a positive attitude towards individuals' intention to purchase a green car depends upon the value that they recognize in the eco-friendly cars. This implied that individuals' decision to accept eco-friendly cars have been influenced by other factors, such as environmental awareness, financial ability, or the vehicles' performance etc. This is in line with the past literature that the study has pointed out several identifications and these are environmental awareness, social attitude, perceived monetary value and the product attitude and these variables were highly impacted on the development applications and purchasing intentions which are necessary and important in managing better development identifications. Further, it has been recorded that the understanding and knowing the impact of environmental analysis is very important and needed as it manages the outcomes in most effective manner (Chen, et al., 2018)Therefore companies have huge responsibility of influencing potential customers through their marketing. Even the study has found that environmental awareness significantly impacts on influencing purchase intention of green cars some of crucial factors such as age level, marital status, government intervention, economic situation of the country have contradictorily act against green car purchase. As such environmental awareness has not been priority among people in this industry and companies should take them into consideration when they plan their strategies to attract eco-friendly car buyers. Some researchers have found that similar outcome from the previous studies while others have found behavioural changes on eco-friendly car purchase (Samuel et al.,2019). Due to the adverse economic conditions within the country has resulted negative effects on car purchase intention whereas we cannot see that from most of the developed countries. With reference to the government influence, eco-friendly and financial incentives have been granted to boost the green car market in the country. Furthermore, the

requirement of implementing and providing facilities for proper infrastructure also identified as a responsibility of the state which previous literature also have suggested the same (Firnkor and Müller, 2012). Import restrictions imposed on all the cars has resulted both positive and negative influence on eco-friendly car purchase which demand decrease for the world recognized green cars on the other hand there is a potential to grow demand for the locally produced electric cars which has been identified in this study whereas no evidence found in the existing literature for import restriction for all cars. But as an incentive for the foreign workers employed in abroad Sri Lankan government has given incentive of tax-free import for the electric cars once they have remitted considerable amount of foreign currency to mitigate both environmental pollution as well as avoid depreciation of Sri Lankan rupee (LKR). This situation has arrived due to the economic downturn in the country and to reduce the number of vehicles in the country. In contrast, some of the governments have announced potential ban of internal combustion engine cars which influence the development of electric cars (Jui-Che Tu and Chun Yang, 2019). Previous study also found that government support on tax credit, legislation to increase environment benefits, introducing penalties for misconduct from both companies/consumers required to promote green cars (Pandey and Kaushik, 2012) and this is in line with the current study results. In contrast, Sri Lankan government proposed rules for free import of electric vehicles to those who employed in a foreign country once they have sent certain number of remittances has been a new pathway to increase the eco-friendly cars without any effort of the green marketing. Because import taxes were such a barrier to the purchase of a vehicle in Sri Lankan context. Similarly, literature found that even government have more power to influence economic system eco-friendly manner non-government organisations (NGO) also have been able to motivate the consumers, firms significantly towards protecting environment (Harangozó and Zilahy, 2015).

6.3.6 Importance of market segmentation on growth of eco-friendly car dealers

Market segmentation regarding the car industry has been seen to be effective and it is vital to know the target customers specially when introducing new product concept. Target market has been identified via eco-friendly customers and non-eco-friendly customers based on their attitudes on the green cars. Car dealer companies of different brands have dealt with both parties and have focused more on eco-friendly consumers which concentrate on environment to promote green cars. Similar categories of market segmentations have been identified by few studies and they have categorised the consumers based on the behaviour and attitude about green products. Marketing and communication strategies have implemented based on their level of the green attitudes to influence towards green product purchase. (Kim et al.,2013, Sanjukta et al.,2020). Therefore, through the finding of the research, it has been found that people who concerned about the environment has been demanded electric cars. However, the rest of the customers have seen to be demandable, but the obstacles were identified with relations to their attitude. Therefore, the market segmentation should be planned effectively and efficiency to achieve the target purpose of protecting environment by securing the profit level. The planning process related to the market segmentation needs utmost effort through knowledgeable and competently selecting and choosing the customer target market, that needs to be reached. Discovering the demands and interests, evaluating the needs of the customers, and then achieving these required through evaluating them must be the primary focus of green car dealers to retain their targeted customers as well as current customers. This will enable car dealer companies to achieve their performances and strategic growth. Furthermore, achieving demand and need of the customers competently increase the brand image and escalate the purchase decision of green cars. Therefore, dealer companies should methodically persuade the customers to select the green car brands towards their target customers through promotion which will enable them to build the brand image and increased purchase intentions from target customers. Therefore, it is concluded that green car market effectively appraises target market segmentation through planning and developing strategy, which efficiently boosts the company in its sustainability and productivity and to achieve environmental sustainability.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTION, LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Conclusion - Achievement of objectives

The goal of the study was to comprehend the mediation effect of branding among the most environmentally friendly aspects of marketing on Sri Lankan consumers' intentions to buy cars. There are a variety of considerations to make when purchasing a car. Given that so many people are worried about how environmentally friendly cars are, a practical situation currently dominates the market (Okada, et al., 2019). Additionally, branding yields results that are comparable. Companies that sell cars should be aware of what customers care about (Xu, et al., 2018). They now play a big role in car sales as a result.

Marketing strategies have been considered as important part of any organisation to achieve their targets and increase the publicity and image of any company. It also helps to attract consumers as well as achieve competitive advantage over other organisations in the industry (Cronin et al,2011). Due to the concern of environmental issues green marketing concept has been a discussion topic around the world. This research was conducted to find out how Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing was affected to purchase intention of the consumers for different car brands. Through the quantitative research method of this research, it has been identified the various relationship between purchase intention and the variables such as environmental awareness, green perceived value, green trust, and mediating effect of brand image. The dependent variable in this study is the intention to buy a car, and the independent variables are environmental awareness, green perceived value, and green trust (Xu, et al., 2018; Lam, et al., 2016; Amin & Tarun, 2020).

In earlier literature, various studies have been presented with comparable results. As the focus areas vary from study to study, these investigations also change. In the literature, various products and various nations are highlighted (Okada, et al., 2019; Lam, et al., 2016; Xu, et al., 2020; Lin, et al., 2017; Al-Quran, et al., 2020). These make various contributions to the research's theoretical underpinnings and literature. To lay the groundwork for the current research and even for future research studies, it is necessary to comprehend each. The three factors "green trust," "perceived value," and "environmental awareness" are the main topics of

the current research. Regarding the environmentally friendly aspects, these three are essential elements. The study's findings make it abundantly clear how these factors are influencing Sri Lankan consumers' intentions to buy cars. The mediation of brand image was also taken into consideration, which gave the study new information (Tariq, et al., 2017; Lee & Lee, 2018). The findings are extremely valuable and make a significant contribution to the literary outcomes. Future research in related fields will benefit greatly from this study. Understanding these is important because they have a significant impact on academic studies in future.

Environmental awareness has been taken as one of the powerful factors that all the car dealers should influence the customers to have higher sales and to obtain strong higher position in the market. To produce successful results, it is essential to understand influencing factors including environmental awareness and attitudes (Okada, et al., 2019). Consumers will have a positive attitude towards purchasing eco-friendly products if they have a high level of environmental knowledge and awareness; as a result, these have significant role in environmental behaviour in advertising the green car concept in the country. Based on this concept, shopping requirements of buyers are highly focused by sellers, and it helps them to execute strategies accordingly. Furthermore, when consumers have more knowledge about the green cars due to the awareness programs demand could shift upward as they have realised the quality and the benefit of the eco-friendly products (Chian et al., 2017)

Many works of literature have suggested that environmental awareness is the knowledge about the impacts of products on the environment. The customer needed to know the positives and negatives (Xu, et al., 2018). The present research has investigated the impact of environmental awareness on the purchasing intentions of cars in Sri Lanka. Hypothesis one was regarding the impact of environmental awareness on the purchasing intentions of the products. This is related to the objective one as well. As per the statistical findings in the research, the relationship is significant. This is a critical outcome resulting from the connections between environmental awareness and the purchasing intentions of the cars. These results show new knowledge for the literature. The outcomes have proved with several past literature as well (Asif, et al., 2018; Suki, 2016; Indriani, et al., 2019; Sreen, et al., 2018; Jung & Seock, 2016; Hsu, et al., 2017; Tan, et al., 2017). These literatures show different scenarios in the different units of analysis, focusing on the impacts of environmental awareness and the purchasing intentions of the buyers. Thus, the results generated in the present research could also be used in the future as a base for similar kinds of research studies. Thus, theoretical contribution of the research outcome is very higher and at the same time, objective achievement also accepted.

Green perceived value is the expected amount of the advantages and outcomes that consumers receive and the expected amount of the outcomes (Lin, et al., 2017). This research has reflected that manufacturer delivered expected quality green cars have been affected to satisfy the customers and it has helped to influence the buyers. With attitude using a stronger influence, companies should try to attract the attention of Sri Lankans towards green cars using commercials and promotions as this could help in influencing the consumers to purchase eco-friendly cars. Therefore, proper green marketing communication required by the dealer companies to achieve highest performances.

The second hypothesis looked into the relationship between perceived green value and the intention to buy a car. The hypothesis is reported as: “Green perceived value in marketing is having a significant positive relationship with the purchase intention of cars among people in Sri Lanka”. This is related to the second objective of the study as well. Understanding these aspects is necessary for the manufacturers to make sure the sales are on track (Wang & Hazen, 2016).. Investigating the connections are necessary to deliver the results. The statistical aspects show the relationship is significant. The results show acceptance of the research objective and acceptance of the two hypotheses in the research. These outcomes have proved by the past literature (Wu, et al., 2015; Ghazali, et al., 2017; Jamal & Sharifuddin, 2015; Trang, et al., 2019; Chaudhary & Bisai, 2018; Degirmenci & Breitner, 2017). These literatures are focused on different products and different nations. Present study also contributing to this pool of literature showing the connections among green perceived value and purchasing intentions in cars in Sri Lankan context. Theoretical contribution towards future research is higher in these findings.

The third objective has been to search for the impact of green trust on the purchasing intentions of cars in Sri Lanka. Green trust is described as the willingness of the customers to purchase and to depend on the environmentally sustainable products based on their performance, credibility, effectiveness. Trust is a concerning factor for any organization. The customer needed to have a significant amount of trust in the products, and they should believe that the products are delivering the value that they need (Cheung, et al., 2015). This study has reflected that customers who have green trust on certain product have been affected positively to the purchase intention. Such concepts have conveyed significant influence on planning green marketing strategy in the car dealer companies. This has helped to achieve higher customer relationship which is critical for any business. Green trust has represented by the third

hypothesis of the research as well. Further, customers should trust that the products are environmentally friendly. The statistical outcomes demonstrating the significance of the relationship. Understanding the green trust is necessary for the marketers to deliver significant outcomes in sales. The study is clear about the connection of green trust and the purchasing intention of the cars in Sri Lankan context. There are many literatures that shows similar outcomes. These past literatures have aided and supported the present finding (Doszhanov & Ahmad, 2015; Nam, et al., 2017; Chen, et al., 2015; Wei, et al., 2017; Agmeka, et al., 2019). Understanding this scenario in Sri Lanka context and related to the cars is a new knowledge contribution towards the literature. This is concerning with understanding the behaviour of the people in the Sri Lanka. The results have contributed towards the literature and added value in future research studies. This is a significant result of the present research.

Brand is a very important factor considered by car purchasers in any country. Cars are higher-end luxury products. Thus, consideration of brand is significant. The mediation of brand image has been checked in the present research. Brand image has been identified as another critical factor to influence the customers to buy eco-friendly cars. This research has reflected that the brand image is important at various stages to encourage purchasing intentions. Companies have identified that it is necessary to increase level of brand image through promotion of green features and environmental benefits of the cars where they could achieve higher customer base. Study has also recognized that increased the environmental awareness, green trust and perceived value have strong and positive influence on brand image as a mediator which consumers attracted to the specific brand and through developed image it has affected to influence the consumer purchase of eco-friendly cars. There are studies that have checked the mediation impact of brand image in different connections (Hien, et al., 2020; Tariq, et al., 2017; Lee & Lee, 2018). Still, the mediation of brand image among eco-friendly aspects and purchasing intention is firstly checked in the present research regarding the cars in Sri Lanka. This is a new contribution to the literature. Brand image was defined in past literature as the perception of the brand that is there in the minds of the customer. This is the ideas, beliefs, and the impressions that the customer is having regarding any product or the service with the brand name (Hien, et al., 2020). Mediation of the brand image in the present study has been measured with the PROCESS macro. The findings demonstrate a direct link between eco-friendly marketing and consumers' intentions to buy. Additionally, it demonstrates that these factors indirectly influence one another through brand image. As a result, brand image affects how

much consumers will spend. Companies must comprehend these elements in order to encourage customers' purchase intentions.

Research has found details about potential customers in Sri Lanka to sell the environmentally friendly cars which car dealers of the country. This research has showed that a considerable number of the population in the Sri Lanka still ignore the value reported by car dealers on environmental protection. It has been due to the lack of effective green promotion and green advertising strategies which also affected due to insufficient brand positioning by those organisations in the marketplace. Moreover, purchase intention has been based on the other demographic factors such as age, marital status, educational level, income level and gender. These also have helped marketers to promote their green cars to the country by obtaining in depth details. Educated adults have more concerned about the green cars and they tend to purchase without considering other factors. Monthly income of the people in SL has been key driver behind green car brand choice and purchase intention with the challenging economic situation of the country. Further, Pearson correlation has been conducted by the researcher to define the trend, strength, and presence of the inter-relationships among environmental awareness, green perceived value, green trust and purchase intention.

During the research qualitative data have been accumulated by the researcher through interviewing the consumers who already possess a car, car dealers, students, few potential car buyers, government officers related to car market in SL. As identified, advertising has been taken a critical place in green cars while tele marketing, social media marketing, billboards and CSR practices have also taken as priority in order to reach wider range of customers raising the consciousness regarding sustainable green car brand positioning. Facebook, company websites, WhatsApp, you tube, twitter have been massively used by younger generation and people who live in the urban cities. Electric car brands such as Tesla, BMW, Toyota, Vega, Micro are much popular brands which have been attracted by the SL consumers. To achieve the sustainability of the companies online marketing strategies such as email, social media advertising, have been utilised by Sri Lankan car dealers while promoting green car concept. The researcher has been identified that, incorporation of the green marketing strategies for the firms assists in recognising changing purchase preference of the consumers as they have reacted to the green marketing concepts in different ways. Most of them considered the green product features but price has been obstacle for due to the worse economic condition. In this difficult socio-economic scenario, price of car has been a key concern for individuals as they are facing

difficulties such as unemployment and inflation, current political unrest within the country and government restrictions on imports. The significance of environmental and green brand value has been considered less when compared with the price by consumers. To achieve sustainability people should act environmentally friendly manner which organisations should focus on the longevity of the sale of car by incorporating eco-friendly strategies and consumers also should have more focus on environmentally friendly behaviour in every aspect of living specially in consumption of products.

It has been identified from this research that people who have more knowledge and awareness about the environment have tend to purchase the green cars than others. Therefore, environmental sustainability has been identified as valuable consideration of car dealers in SL to achieve their sustainable growth. Implementing effective marketing segmentation strategies car dealers have been identified and able to shorten their product offering to the potential buyers based on their demand. It has also been recognised that in Sri Lanka, men are interested to purchase green cars than women in their shopping behaviours. In this case car dealers have a responsibility of make awareness programs to the female buyers and also, they have concentrated on focusing higher income earners as the people considered the car investment is an important decision in their lives. The professional population who has been realised the criticality of the environmental benefits have been targeted to increase the sales of green cars.

7.2 Contribution

The aim of the research has been to examine eco-friendly aspects of marketing on car purchase intention in Sri Lanka. The research contributes to the theoretical expansion of the model, efficiency, and the growth of a policy in the literature on eco-friendly car dealers (Hong et al., 2016). Green cars marketing and selling in Sri Lanka have been addressed as an economic and environmental development which related to Sri Lanka's sustainable development. Marketing is still critical concept at the course of trading of cars, eco-friendly products research, policy making in these areas and importation of goods. Although environment is at a high risk due to most of human activities, protecting it is the most important task today. (Nunes, 2010).

7.2.1 Theoretical contribution

The most critical contribution of this research is that there is strong theoretical evidence of eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on car purchase intention which was also the main topics of the current research. Three factors "green trust," "perceived value," and "environmental awareness" were the essential elements which clearly found the relationship to purchase intention of Sri Lankan consumers. The study's findings make it abundantly clear how these factors are influencing Sri Lankan consumers' intentions to buy cars. This is an expansion of competitive literature on eco-friendly aspects of marketing on car purchase intention. The results have contributed towards the literature and added value in future research studies. Therefore it provide knowledge of literature on green marketing factors of car industry.

This is the first study that used the mediation effect of brand image checked between the identified areas regarding the cars in Sri Lanka and which is new knowledge and contributes to the literature (Tariq, et al., 2017; Lee & Lee, 2018). In other words, we can say that green brand image successfully allows firms to increase green purchases by employing green branding, green promotions. This is a significant result of the present research. The theoretical value of these findings is higher.

The conceptual framework established for this study provides a reliable framework for examining influential factors of multidimensional green marketing aspects on car purchase by examining literature on brand image as mediating factor which theory suggesting it makes the huge impact on the organizational strategic direction development (Tan, et al., 2022).

Therefore, it provides knowledge of the literature on green cars marketing to the worldwide manufacturers and car dealers who are looking to invest in emerging country Sri Lanka. It provides information on car importation of green cars to examine main factors that determine competitiveness among different brands in the country as well as other developing countries in the region (Sauer et al., 2004). This study has satisfactorily provided an adequate amount of theoretical information to the marketing scholars, business managers, government and non-government organisation who usually use this information to generate strategies in their various conditions.

7.2.2 Practical contribution

In fact, the research reveals that certain decisions able to help increase the environmental protection through influencing consumers. Therefore, the achievement of eco-friendly environment could be achieved through green marketing promotions, understanding of the and maintaining better relationships such as consumers, manufacturing companies and government etc (Mishra and Sharma 2014). As such maintaining a solid relationship with them is a must to have strong emotional connection between brands and consumers to have sustainable future specially in developing country like Sri Lanka.

Notably this study confirm that environmental awareness is most critical factor which influence the consumer purchase intention. Therefore, the procedures need to conduct awareness programs for the environment protection in timely basis influencing people to turn into green cars from conventional fuel vehicles to mitigate the greenhouse emissions to the environment. The activists are fundamentally needed to make people aware though social media marketing to convince them about the criticality of switching into eco-friendly cars. Consequently, companies should convey the message that they comply and practicing eco-friendly processes to influence consumers (Suki, 2016). It was also noted that even the digitalisation has changed the way of marketing communication to promote green cars and formulated the strategies accordingly, other advertising methods are still important to use depending on the consumer's adoption and company's capacity of the investments.

Identification of factors which helps to implement an effective green marketing strategies could be helpful for the car dealer companies to succeed in the potential green car market and provision of proper training for their staff, increased participation of employees to generate ideas are considered as critical. Therefore, those companies should understand nature of the marketing of luxury products such as green cars and what to do and the way use digital advertising to create good relationship with their stakeholders (Lee, K.H., 2009).

Online platforms have considered an easier for some customers as they can have the details of green car features as well as other related information before taking the purchase decision. As a necessary requirement country's proper infrastructure should be implemented equally without restricting to main cities as identified in this research as a potential long term government strategy which car industry could benefits. Similarly, government incentive tax

subsidies, avoid restrictions on imports, helping to install solar panel systems to generate electricity, facilitating to implement common electric car charging points are few things that may have the potential to make continuous improvements in the environment through the promotion of green cars.

Practical importance and theoretical importance of the research are very high, and thus, it should be mentioned that the research is highly important towards the development of the research conclusions in the future. Further, this research is important for the car manufactures around the world to take decisions regarding the marketing and sales of the products as well.

7.3 Research Limitations

Limitations and gaps identified in this study can be further raised in future research to improve results. Firstly, primary sources of data collected to the study. Data sources are credible and reliable. Researcher used both qualitative and quantitative data as this study aimed to enhance the accuracy and credibility. Quantitative analysis leads to standardisation of information and data while qualitative data analysis deals in-depth knowledge of requirement in the business environment (Snyder, 2019). These data facilitate to achieve research objectives and questions positively. There is no choice of gathering data when you do research yourself and this is a time-consuming task. Research must be well planned and budgeted to have exact information someone need. Once you have collected data after careful organisation, researcher must evaluate the data. Those results must be interpreted and presented to provide future research with its limitations (Schünemann et al, 2019). The limits are related to results and the methodology. The limits are related to results and the methodology. The study was mainly based on managers/owners in all car dealerships which participated in responding to the questions and they are the key decision makers. Also, some consumers who owned cars, professionals, government officers, students who are knowledgeable about the car industry who have capacity to express issues related to car purchase behaviour, marketing strategies and influenced detailed information which was essential to answer research questions for this research (Labrecque et al., 2020). However, information provided by those parties do not always reflect their activities in connection with marketing strategies, environmental awareness or they may not have sufficient technical and factual knowledge of their activities. This study focused on green marketing strategies used by car dealers in Sri Lanka. If the secondary data collection methods used in this study, it could have provided broader range for analysing things

from various legal sources such as books, journals, newspaper articles or other published sources without limiting only to the primary data. Such research methods could be chosen for analysing information from available sources in the future research.

Eco friendliness and green marketing expands beyond the car market and is not only related to the business world. The research study limited itself to researching a motor car industry through the dealer network system. In practice, there could be other industries in the country which this research can be undertaken to have more understanding in terms of eco-friendliest aspects of marketing which have been specified in the current study.

7.4 Recommendations

The important contribution of this research to knowledge is has been to identify the connection between eco-friendly aspects of marketing and its affect for the consumer purchase intention. Most critically it was also understood how green marketing works within the context developing economy. As a developing country, Sri Lanka have been facing for a economic downturn last few years and it has been an obstacle for the successful implementation of eco-friendly marketing and make awareness of the people to buy green cars. Less environmental knowledge and financial hardships of the consumers have resulted to make a big effort by marketing professionals to explain the importance of green cars and sell them. If this study could have been conducted in a country which prevail less issues, the situation would have been different. Therefore, there is a need of green marketing model which is applicable to all economic settings.

Finally, it is not essential to oversimplify multiple views of this study from the point of issues. in contrast it is argued that and general contextual analysis of intervention of car dealer companies supply information on how to understand mediation in this market. The priority of this study has been achieved by providing the theoretical and practical implications in the view of car market in Sri Lanka and for the economy and customer needs in daily running of car dealership.

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Annexure 1: Motor car growth Year on Year

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Annexure :02 - New Registered Motor Car Data -2020

Source: Department of Motor Traffic

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Annexure :03 - Qualitative research approach Design diagram

Annexure 04: Classification of the interviewees; distribution by sectors, companies, and geographic scope of activities

Code of Interviewee	Sector	Region	Profession	Age-Group	Gender
P1	Auto Dealer	Western Province	Marketing Manager	46-50	Male
P2	Auto Dealer	Western Province	Engineering	51-55	Female
P3	Car Owner-Government	Southern Province	Government Servant	36-40	Male
P4	Car Owner-Government	Eastern province	Clerical officer	36-40	Female
P5	Car Owner-Government	Sabaragamuwa province	Teacher	31-35	Female
P6	Auto Dealer	Western Province	Managing Director	56-60	Male
P7	Auto Dealer	North Central province	Manager	46-50	Male
P8	Car Owner-Private Company	Uva province	Sales representative	41-45	Male
P9	Group company	Central Province	Marketing Manager	41-45	Male
P10	Group company	Western Province	CEO	46-45	Male
P11	Group company	Western Province	Deputy Managing Director	46-50	Male
P12	Car Owner	Southern Province	Bank executive	26-30	Female
P13	Car Owner	Eastern province	Sales Executive	31-35	Male
P14	Car Owner	Northern province	Small Business Owner	26-30	Male
P15	Department of Motor traffic authority	Western Province	Deputy Managing Director	56-60	Male
P16	Car Owner	Northern province	Audit Manager	36-40	Female
P17	Car Owner	Sabaragamuwa province	Biomedical Engineer	41-45	Male
P18	Auto Dealer	Western Province	Manager	46-50	Male
P19	Auto Dealer	Western Province	Sales representative	31-35	Male
P20	Auto Dealer	North Central province	Manager	36-40	Male
P21	Car Owner	Southern Province	Lawyer	36-40	Male
P22	Car Owner	Uva province	Housewife	26-30	Female
P23	Car Owner	Central Province	Sales Executive	41-45	Male
P24	Car Owner	Western Province	Hairdresser	36-40	Male
P25	Car Owner	Southern Province	Sales Manager	41-45	Male
P26	Car Owner	North Western province	Housewife	46-50	Female
P27	Car Owner	North Western province	Professor	31-35	Male
P28	Academic	Western Province	Professor	41-45	Male
P29	Academic	Northern province	Professor	41-45	Female
P30	Academic	Southern Province	Student	18-20	Male

Annexure:05 - Survey Questionnaires

Mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on Car purchasing Intention Sri Lanka

I am Irangi Shashika Athulath Mudalige one of the students in University of West of Scotland, London campus. This survey is designed as a part of an ongoing research ‘Mediation effect of branding between Eco-friendliest aspects of marketing on Car purchasing Intention Sri Lanka’ Please note that the responses you provide are completely anonymous and confidential. The research outcome and report will not include reference to any individuals. The compiler of the questionnaire has the sole ownership of the completed questionnaire and make sure not to sign your name.

There are two parts of the questionnaire which is providing the demographic variables and the next part is providing the questions regarding eco-friendly aspects of marketing, purchasing intention and branding.

Directions

1. Please read the questions carefully
2. Mark (X) in the most appropriate answer

Part I – Demographic Information

1) Gender

Male		Female	
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2) Age

20-30 years	
31-40 years	
41-50 years	

3) Marital Status

Married		Single	
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4) Income Level (Monthly)

500 000 – 10 000 000	
10 000 000 – 15 000 000	
15 000 000 – 20 000 000	
More than 20 000 000	

Part II – Variable Measuring Questions

➤ **Environmental Awareness**

No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I am very knowledgeable about environmental issues occurred due to automobiles					
2	Compared to the average person, I am more familiar with issues related to the environment by the automobiles					
3	I know how to select vehicles that produce the least carbon emissions					
4	I understand the environmental effect of vehicle consumption					
5	I know that the adoption of a hybrid car is more sustainable as compared to the adoption of a conventional car					

➤ **Green Perceived Value**

No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
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6	This brand's environmental function provides very good value for me					
7	This brand's environmental performance meets my expectations					
8	I purchase this brand because it is environmentally friendly					
9	I purchase this brand because it has, an environmental benefit than other products					

➤ **Green Trust**

No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
10	I believe that this product's environmental image is generally reliable					
11	I think that this product's environmental functionality is generally dependable					
12	Overall, I believe that this product's environmental claims are trustworthy					
13	This product's environmental performance meets my expectations					

➤ **Brand Image**

No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
14	Some characteristics of that specific product come to my mind promptly					
15	I know what that specific product looks like					
16	I can quickly recall the logo of that specific product					
17	I can differentiate the brand from other brands					
18	I can recognize this brand among the other brands					

➤ **Purchasing Intention**

No	Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
19	In the near future, I will consider buying an eco-friendly car					
20	In the near future, I will consider switching to an eco-friendly car					
21	I am preferring eco-friendly cars than the other cars					
22	I prefer an eco-friendly car even if it is more expensive as compared to a normal car					
23	I think purchasing an eco-friendly car is a valuable green purchase					

Thank You !!!

Annexure: 06 - Ethical Approval

24/03/2020

Dear Irangi Shashika Athulath Mudalige,

Your application 9691 : Ethical Approval , submission 9175, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

There is still some confusing regarding the methodological and methods terminology, but there is no issue related to ethics.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean